

AN ETHICAL AI TAXONOMY AND INITIAL GUIDELINES FOR TEACHER-AI COMPLEMENTARITY

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.1 (D3.1) of the TAICo (Teacher-AI Complementarity) project forms part of Work Package 3 (WP3), which focuses on understanding the technical aspects of AI systems, with a particular attention to the design and development features that support teacher complementarity. This deliverable aims to conceptualise the current landscape of teacher-facing AI tools used in education, map their design and development features to implications for teacher competence, and propose visionary scenarios of human-centred and ethical AI to support teacher-AI complementarity.

D3.1 comprises two main tasks. The first task involves the development of an initial AI taxonomy that operationalises the technical aspects of AI systems into target constructs representing technical capabilities that can assist teachers in their professional practice. Drawing on a review of existing human-AI frameworks and taxonomies, the proposed taxonomy identifies key constructs and features within the AI design and development pipeline that influence the effectiveness, efficacy, and ethical dimensions of teacher-AI complementarity. The second task (Task 3.1) runs concurrently and consists of a systematic review of the design, development, and deployment features of teacher-facing AI technologies across diverse educational contexts, as reported in empirical studies. Using the initial taxonomy as an analytical lens, the review was conducted iteratively to develop a comprehensive and evidence-based understanding of the current landscape of teacher-facing AI tools in education. This process supports both the validation and refinement of the proposed taxonomy. By mapping the design and development features identified in the reviewed studies to their implications for teachers, the review highlights research gaps and generates interaction-oriented insights, which inform preliminary guidelines for the future development of human-centred and ethical AI systems supporting teacher complementarity piloting within the TAICo project.

This deliverable is structured into six sections. Section 1 provides an overview of D3.1, while Section 2 presents the theoretical and empirical background underpinning the taxonomy, highlighting current research gaps related to the ethical use of AI by teachers. Section 3 describes the taxonomy development process and introduces its key constructs, which guide the categorisation of studies in the systematic literature review. As part of this development, five teaming levels are proposed to conceptualise varying modes of interaction between teachers and AI systems, emphasising interaction-related features as critical design considerations. Section 4 outlines the methodology and findings of the systematic review, including a mapping of teacher-facing AI tools across teaming levels and their implications for teachers. Section 5 discusses the emerging findings and derives initial technical, ethical, and practical design guidelines for AI systems to support teacher complementarity. Finally, Section 6 delineates the connections between D3.1 and related tasks across the TAICo work packages.

1. Introduction

TAICo, as part of the Horizon Europe framework program, undertakes a Research and Innovation Action with the primary goal of designing, developing, implementing, and validating a model of Teacher-AI Complementarity applicable across the broader teaching profession, including primary and secondary general education, higher education, and continuing education and training.

Work Package 3 (WP3) focuses on the design and development features of AI for teacher complementarity. It aims to thoroughly understand the current landscape of AI tools used in education, map their design and development features to implications for teachers, and build future scenarios of human-centred and ethical AI for teacher-AI complementarity.

The purpose of Deliverable 3.1 (D3.1) is to report on the development of an initial AI taxonomy and provide initial guidelines for the design and development of human-centred and ethical AI supporting teacher complementarity. Drawing from existing frameworks and taxonomies, the AI taxonomy proposed in this deliverable identifies key constructs and features in the AI design and development pipeline that impact the effectiveness, efficacy, and ethics of teacher-AI complementarity.

D3.1 stems from Task 3.1 (T3.1), which involves a systematic review of the design, development, and deployment features of teacher-facing AI technologies across various educational contexts. The systematic review contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape of teacher-facing AI tools used in education. By mapping their design and development features to implications for teachers, initial guidelines for the future design and development of AI for the TAICo project are generated.

It is worth noting that the development of the AI taxonomy proposed here and the systematic review of AI technologies were conducted iteratively. On one hand, the design and development features identified in the AI taxonomy were used to shape the labelling and coding of the identified papers from the systematic literature review. For instance, for each paper, we systematically coded whether and how it reflected each taxonomy feature. These predefined features functioned as labels for coding, ensuring consistency across papers and enabling comparisons. When a study did not explicitly identify these elements, we coded them based on the described system functionalities. In this way, the taxonomy directly determined what aspects of each AI tool we considered as related to the teaching tasks and how we organised and interpreted the evidence. On the other hand, empirical evidence collected from the systematic review was used to evaluate and refine the characteristics and dimensions conceptualised in the AI taxonomy. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the work included in D3.1.

Fig.1 An overview of the work in D3.1

D3.1 is the first deliverable in WP3 and contributes to the other tasks and deliverables within the work package. For instance, the design and development features identified in the AI taxonomy will inform the design and development of the AI interface in T3.3. These features will also contribute to the design of the AI component of the TAICo model in WP1. The initial guidelines will be further refined in collaboration with education sector stakeholders during co-design sessions in T3.2.

The rest of this report is structured as follows. First, the background section illustrates the significance of developing an AI taxonomy for the ethical use of AI by teachers. Section 3 introduces the characteristics and dimensions identified in the AI taxonomy and how a systematic review was structured around these dimensions. Section 4 presents the results of the systematic literature review and mapping the design and development features of AI tools to their implications for teachers. Based on these results, Section 5 generates and presents the initial guidelines. Finally, Section 6 outlines how D3.1 relates to other TAICo work packages and tasks.

2. Background

2.1. AI holds complex benefits and challenges for teachers

The rapid advancement of AI in recent years presents global societies with profound and complex challenges and opportunities for the future of education. AI is increasingly recognized as a strategic investment, offering significant potential to enhance student learning outcomes, improve the efficiency of teaching, professional learning, and administrative tasks, and support effective pedagogical practices. For example, previous literature has shown that AI can help teachers save time in their practice (Roy et al., 2024) and improve instructional effectiveness (Wang et al., 2024).

However, the integration of AI within educational settings also raises substantial concerns. For instance, as AI becomes more integrated into the classroom, there are growing concerns about the potential de-professionalisation of teaching (Berendt et al., 2020). Felix and Webb (2024) also raised a similar concern that teachers may lose their skills due to the

over-reliance on AI to perform teaching tasks such as lesson planning, marking, and providing feedback. Furthermore, the integration of generative AI into educational environments also raises significant questions about its impact on teachers' various higher-order thinking skills, particularly through its influence on critical and reflective thinking practices. The point about the automation of routine tasks inadvertently depriving individuals of opportunities to cultivate their judgment and cognitive resilience, leaving them ill-prepared for situations that require exceptional thinking, is reminded periodically by scholars (e.g. Bainbridge, 1983; Cukurova, 2025). For example, Lee and colleagues (2025) indicated that engaging with generative AI tools can significantly modify the creative and reflective practices of teachers and other knowledge workers.

The potential dehumanisation of teaching and education in general is another important consideration when integrating AI in teaching and learning. When AI in education is considered in a narrow sense as replacement of teachers and as lonely individual learners working on their own with an AI system (e.g. an AI learning companion), this might indeed lead learners to prioritise information gathering and declarative knowledge acquisition over procedural and tacit knowledge and wisdom which comes through rich human experiences in the real world (Cukurova, 2025). Additionally, AI systems, particularly those relying heavily on large-scale data analytics and algorithm-driven instruction, have an inherent tendency to privilege uniformity and predictability, often at the expense of diversity, creativity, and cultural specificity. This raises significant concerns regarding the potential standardisation of teaching and learning experiences, which may inadvertently lead to a homogenised and exclusionary educational landscape. This issue is further complicated by inherent biases embedded within AI systems, as these technologies often draw upon data and narratives predominantly originating from wealthier and technologically advanced countries. This can perpetuate existing cultural, linguistic, and socioeconomic biases, reinforcing systemic inequalities and exacerbating exclusion. Recent research indicates even the most advanced state-of-the-field LLM models have implicit and explicit biases embedded in them when they are used in educational practice like feedback provision (Du et al., 2025). And systematic literature reviews on data-driven educational technologies (e.g. Gauthier et al., 2022) highlight notable gaps that only a few studies have rigorously evaluated whether these technologies genuinely reduce teacher bias or promote equitable teaching practices.

Previous research indicates the central importance of human agency in addressing, or to a certain extent mitigating, these challenges. For instance, Frostenson (2015) argued that a perceived de-professionalisation of the teaching profession is often attributed to a loss of professional autonomy. Meanwhile, keeping AI systems under effective human oversight, thus ensuring that human agency is enacted when and if the need occurs, is also vital for the protection of core human competence against the potential negative effects of algorithmic decision-making. Furthermore, protecting teacher agency may benefit the shaping of human-AI interaction as a form of partnership where each party's strengths are leveraged and weaknesses are mitigated (Cukurova, 2025; Molenaar, 2022). It is important to note that agency in human-AI contexts is not located solely within the individual human or the machine, but is distributed across complex human-AI interaction. Protecting human agency does not mean isolating human decision-making from AI, but rather managing the entanglement of human and machine agency during the process of human-AI interaction (Code, 2025). Driven by these theoretical and empirical insights regarding the importance of teacher agency as a

key concept in achieving an ethical teacher-AI complementarity. this deliverable specifically focuses on the interactions between teachers and AI tools to investigate what design, development, and deployment features are related to teachers' agency.

2.2. A need for an AI taxonomy for teacher-AI Complementarity

Given the importance of transparency, accountability, fairness, and ethical considerations in social contexts such as education, it is essential for not only teachers but also other stakeholders to clearly understand AI design features and decision-making processes. Consequently, a taxonomy is needed to organize information about AI used for teachers in a structured manner, making it easier to identify, study, and communicate about these technologies. For instance, a taxonomy can provide a clear structure for teachers to understand different types of AI tools used for teaching tasks. Although there are various AI tools designed to support teachers, it may not be clear for teachers how these teacher-facing AI tools work, how they interact with the AI tools to make full use of the tools, and what are the potential risks of them. This lack of exposure to credible AI information may limit their integration of AI tools in their teaching (Hazzan-Bishara et al., 2025).

Moreover, delineating the differences between various types of teacher-facing AI allows designers and developers to make more informed design and development decisions. By clearly understanding how different AI approaches operate in teaching tasks, what their capabilities and limitations are, and which teaching contexts they are best suited for, designers can select methods and focus on the design and development features that align with specific pedagogical goals and constraints. This clarity helps ensure that AI systems are not only technically appropriate but also efficient, reliable, and aligned with instructional design. Furthermore, by offering clear definitions of the design features and distinctions among AI systems, a taxonomy can enable researchers to compare studies about teacher-facing AI. It introduces a list of terminologies that reduce ambiguity, making it easier to identify similarities, differences, and relationships across research findings. Therefore, researchers can better synthesize evidence, evaluate progress across subfields, and build on each other's work with greater precision and coherence (Weidlich et al., 2025). Lastly, the taxonomy can also help policymakers to detail the policy or regulation of different types of teacher-facing AI tools. Given that different types of teacher-facing AI may have distinct impacts, developing more detailed and differentiated policies is essential. Such policies help ensure that each category of teacher-facing AI can leverage its strengths while mitigating its specific risks. By analysing the design, development, and deployment features of different types of teacher-facing AI, it becomes possible to identify the necessary standards for safety and reliability, privacy protection, fairness, and transparency and accountability that each type requires.

Although some existing taxonomies or frameworks address AI in education, most focus solely on the AI techniques employed or the pedagogical tasks they support. For example, Aiken and Epstein (2000) raised two meta principles of AIED system: (1) "AIED technology should not diminish the student along any of the fundamental dimensions of human being", and (2) "AIED technology should augment the student along at least one of the fundamental dimensions of human being". Based on these principles, they have proposed 10 principles for designing AIED systems as ethical guidelines. Also, Holmes and colleagues (2022) conducted a survey study about the ethical issues of AI in Education and summarised the results from 17

experts in this research field. The results identified three main foci, namely the ethics of data, computational approaches and education. Furthermore, the overlaps between the three foci emerged further concerns about the ethics of data in AI in general, the ethics of data in education, and the ethics of algorithms applied in educational contexts. Yet, these frameworks neglect the crucial element of human agency in human-AI interaction. There remains a lack of information about the affordances provided by AI, how teachers interact with AI, and how AI decisions are made in teaching practices. Moreover, although there were existing AI taxonomies and frameworks addressing the technical characteristics of AI (OECD, 2022), types of AI agents (Russell et al., 1995), and types of human–AI interactions (Crowley et al., 2022), they did not specifically focus on educational contexts.

Therefore, T3.1 focuses on creating a taxonomy of teacher-facing AI system features in education that are specifically relevant for teacher-AI complementarity. This includes, but is not limited to, the AI's specific purpose, modelling techniques, provided affordances, human-AI interface, and different types of human-AI interactions. By mapping these features to their implications in teaching practice, teachers and other stakeholders can gain a better understanding of different types of teacher-facing AI and their impact on teaching. Furthermore, this approach provides valuable insights for the future design and development of teacher-facing AI.

2.3. Towards an ethical AI taxonomy for teacher-AI Complementarity

The use of AI by teachers introduces several potential risks that warrant careful consideration. First, algorithmic bias embedded in AI models can lead to unfair or inaccurate assessments, recommendations, or classifications, thereby reinforcing existing inequities among students if teachers rely on AI without critical consideration (Du et al., 2025). Second, issues of accountability emerge when decision-making becomes partially automated, making it difficult to attribute responsibility for errors or harmful outcomes to either the teacher, the institution, or the AI system itself (Baker & Hawn, 2022). Third, the opacity of many AI models limits transparency, as teachers may be unable to discern how outputs are generated or to provide justifiable explanations to students and parents (Chaudhry et al., 2022).

Teachers are pivotal in addressing the ethical challenges of AI in education. Previous research argued that Interpersonal dynamics of learning should remain central, and automation must not undermine these essential human interactions (Adams et al., 2023). Teachers play an important role in balancing the integration of AI-assisted tools with the maintenance of human-centred pedagogical practices. They are not only end users of the teacher-facing AI tools, but also the mediators between the ethical framework and the teaching practice. Meanwhile, teachers also take direct responsibility of using AI and supporting students to use AI in assessment. Teachers need to be able to critique and trust AI recommendations (Nazaretsky et al., 2022) and remain accountable for AI-driven actions under their supervision, while being aware of potential biases, training protocols, and optimization goals of the AI systems. Therefore, teachers' agency have been considered as a key factor to address the ethical issues in integrating AI in teaching (Yan et al., 2025).

Based on a recent literature review on the ethical issues of AI in education, preserving human agency in the design, development, and deployment of AI is considered as essential

for ensuring that AI systems promote transparency, fairness, user autonomy, and human oversight (Yan et al., 2025). However, current design and development of teacher-facing AI systems remain heavily focusing on the automation of teaching tasks such as lesson plan creation or content generation, neglecting fostering teachers' agency in the use of AI. A clear taxonomy is needed to categorise the interactions between teachers and AI to move towards high teacher agency interactions.

3. The Development of a Teacher-facing AI Taxonomy

Taxonomies provide a structure and an organisation to the knowledge of a field, thus enabling researchers to study the relationships among concepts and, therefore, to hypothesise about these relationships (Glass & Vessey, 2002). The TAICo project aims to develop a teacher-facing AI taxonomy to identify the key features of the interactions between teachers and the AI tools, as well as the design and development features of the teacher-facing AI tools which are related to the interaction features. This section introduces the development process of the teacher-facing AI taxonomy. The first section describes the approach applied for the development of the teacher-facing AI taxonomy. Then, the initial version of the taxonomy is presented with detailed descriptions as well as examples of each characteristic.

3.1. An Approach for developing teacher-facing AI taxonomy

We adapted the taxonomy development method proposed by Nickerson et al. (2013), which includes two different approaches and seven steps (Fig. 2). First, we identified the meta-characteristics of the taxonomy, which in this case is the different types of interactions between teachers and AI tools. Next, we established both objective and subjective ending conditions to determine when to terminate the iterative development process. The objective ending condition is that no dimensions or characteristics were added, merged, or split in the last iteration (Sowa & Zachman, 1992). Regarding the subjective ending conditions, the taxonomy should be both comprehensive and explanatory. This means it must cover all teacher-facing AI tools identified in the previous literature review and provide detailed explanations of these tools through descriptions of their characteristics.

Fig.2 A taxonomy development method proposed by Nickerson et al. (2013)

Based on Nickerson et al. (2013), taxonomy development can follow either an empirical-to-conceptual or a conceptual-to-empirical approach. Aligning with the future-oriented vision of Horizon Europe’s funding goals, the TAICo AI taxonomy not only inductively considers existing teacher-facing AI tools but also anticipates future scenarios of teacher-AI complementarity. Therefore, this work applied a conceptual-to-empirical approach, taking into account both the coverage of existing AI tools and the vision for future AI tools.

For instance, we first conceptualized different types of teacher-AI interactions and the AI affordances that support these interactions based on previous literature, including, but not limited to, research on various types of human-AI collaboration (Crowley et al., 2022), taxonomies for AI agent types (Russell et al., 1995), and general AI taxonomies (OECD, 2022). Subsequently, a systematic literature review was conducted to collect teacher-facing AI tools reported in prior studies, which were then used to examine these characteristics and dimensions. The AI taxonomy was iteratively revised until the ending conditions were met. The results of the systematic literature review are presented in Section 4 of this deliverable. In addition to the systematic literature review, two focus groups were conducted within the TAICo project research team, in which TAICo partners mapped their use cases to the initial AI taxonomy. By discussing whether any TAICo cases could not be categorised using the initial taxonomy, these focus groups were used to determine whether the ending conditions had been satisfied. Appendix.3 showed the details of how TAICo cases mapped to the proposed level of teacher-AI teaming. It is worth noting that, the mapping is preliminary results. The mapping may change depending on the new design of the AI system in TAICo cases.

3.2. An overview of the teacher-facing AI taxonomy

The TAICo teacher-facing AI taxonomy consists of two main dimensions: the teacher-AI interaction dimension and the AI Agent Characterisation dimension. Within the interaction dimension, we define five levels of teacher-AI teaming to represent different types of interactions between teachers and AI tools, adapted from Crowley and colleagues' (2022) hierarchical framework for collaborative artificial intelligence.

The AI Agent Characterisation dimension is described at both the agent level and the model level, as AI tools consist of multiple AI agents, and each AI agent consists of different AI models. At the agent level, adapting from Russell and Norvig's (1995) five types of AI agents, we define five types of AI agents for teacher-facing AI and describe the various tasks associated with each type. At the model level, we adapted OECD's (2022) framework for classifying AI systems in educational contexts, describing different types of AI models, the data used by the models, the algorithms employed, model evaluation methods, and model evolution capabilities.

Furthermore, we define different types of interfaces that connect the teacher-AI interaction dimension with the AI Agent Characterisation dimension. The design of these interfaces serves as an intermediary in the sense that interface design is heavily influenced by the capabilities of the AI agent while simultaneously shaping the types of teaming between teachers and AI tools.

Fig.3 An overview of the TAICo Teacher-facing AI Taxonomy

3.3. AI Agent Characterisation Dimension

3.3.1. AI agent type

A simple reflex agent only acts on the basis of the current perception of the teaching or learning tasks, ignoring the rest of the perceived history. The agent function is based on the condition-action rule: "if condition, then action".

A model-based agent can handle partially observable learning and teaching contexts. Its current state about learning and teaching is stored inside the agent, maintaining a structure that describes the part of the process of learning and teaching which cannot be seen.

The goal-based agent expands on the capabilities of the model-based agents by using "goal" information. Goal information describes situations that are desirable in the learning and teaching contexts. This provides the agent a way to choose among multiple possibilities, selecting the one which reaches a goal state.

A utility-based agent has the ability to choose actions that maximise the expected utility of learning and teaching outcomes. Utility is a numerical value that represents the desirability or satisfaction of an outcome, quantifying how well an agent achieves its goals while balancing trade-offs in learning or teaching. These utilities are initially predefined by the AI designer or developer. However, the weights assigned to different utilities can be adapted to teachers' preferences through interactions between teachers and the AI agent.

A learning agent begins in unknown learning and teaching contexts and gradually surpasses the bounds of their initial knowledge about teaching and learning. It can gather feedback from teaching and learning environments to assess the agent's performance and decide how the performance element can be adjusted to yield better outcomes. A learning agent must be able to modify its behaviour over time based on new data collected in the learning and teaching contexts or feedback provided by teachers.

3.3.2. AI model Information

3.3.2.1. Model Type and algorithms

Symbolic AI: Symbolic or knowledge-based artificial intelligence in education relies on human-defined logical rules about teaching and learning to draw conclusions or make decisions based on a structured set of conditions. These conditions, such as learning objectives, learning behaviours, student profiles, or assessment criteria, are explicitly described and connected through logical relationships. Such models are typically expressed through formal languages like mathematical logic (using if/then statements or formulas), or through agent-based and event-driven models that simulate the process of teaching and learning. Symbolic AI continues to play an important role in education technology, particularly in intelligent tutoring systems, curriculum planning, and learning analytics tools that optimise teaching strategies or learning pathways.

Statistical AI: Statistical or data-driven AI models, such as neural networks, deep learning systems, and genetic algorithms, learn to recognise patterns and make predictions from large sets of data rather than relying on human-defined rules or expert knowledge. In education contexts, these models make use of data collected from the learning process and the environment where learning happens to recognise significant patterns of learning and teaching behaviours, as well as predict learning and teaching outcomes.

Unlike symbolic AI, which depends on explicit and interpretable rules, statistical AI extracts and represents knowledge implicitly within its data patterns. This makes it highly effective at identifying complex trends in student behaviour or performance, though the reasoning behind its decisions is often less transparent and harder for educators to interpret.

Hybrid AI: A hybrid AI model combines both symbolic and statistical approaches of knowledge representation. In educational contexts, hybrid models can learn from previous educational data to recognise important patterns of learning and teaching behaviours. Meanwhile, experts can also set rules for the models based on the learning theories and their pedagogical experiences.

3.3.2.2. Data

Data forms the foundation of artificial intelligence, serving as the essential resource from which AI systems learn, adapt, and generate meaningful insights. Therefore, it is important to describe the data information when describing an AI system. In this taxonomy, we mainly focus on data context, data modality, and educational constructs. For instance, data context describes who the data was collected from, students, teachers, or the learning environment. Data modality refers to the type or form of data through which information is represented or captured. Common data modalities include textual data, rating data, log data, video data, audio data, physiological data, sensor or motion data, and image data (Alwahaby et al., 2022). Educational constructs are abstract concepts or theoretical ideas used to describe, explain, or measure aspects of learning, teaching, and educational experience. We used a framework developed by Knobbout and Stappen (2020) to categorise the education constructs into learning environment, learning process, and learning outcome.

3.3.2.3. Evaluation

The evaluation of an AI model is a crucial characteristic in determining its effectiveness, reliability, and suitability for its intended educational purpose. Model evaluation ensures that the system performs accurately and fairly across different learning contexts and student groups. Common performance metrics of an AI model include accuracy (the proportion of correct predictions), precision and recall (how well the model identifies relevant instances), and F1-score (a balanced measure of precision and recall). For predictive or continuous outcomes, measures such as mean squared error (MSE) or R^2 (coefficient of determination) are often used.

3.3.2.4. Evolution

Model evolution is used to describe the capability of an AI model to continuously adapt and improve its performance by updating its parameters or structure in response to new input data. Based on OECD's (2022) AI framework, there are three categories, namely no evolution during operation, evolution during operation through passive interaction, and evolution during operation through active interaction. No evolution means the Dataset is static and does not change over time. An AI model is given a dataset and learns patterns or associations of learning and teaching behaviours from it.

Evolution during operation through passive interaction in education refers to an AI model's ability to adapt continuously as it receives new learning data from students' ongoing activities, such as quiz results, time spent on tasks, or interaction patterns within a learning platform. Although the AI system does not control these behaviours, it analyses them in real time to refine its understanding of each learner's progress and adjust recommendations or feedback accordingly.

Evolution during operation through active interaction in education refers to an AI model that actively engages with the learning environment and adapts based on the outcomes of its interactions with teachers and students.

3.3.3. AI task

Artificial intelligence in education performs a variety of tasks that enhance teaching, learning, and decision-making by analysing data, detecting patterns, predicting outcomes, and adapting to individual learners. Adapting from OECD's (2022) framework of AI, we described six types of AI tasks in educational contexts to understand what the tasks of AI in teacher-AI complementarity are.

Recognition involves identifying and categorising different types of data collected from learning and teaching contexts, such as images, videos, audio, or text, using supervised learning techniques.

Event detection connects data points to identify patterns of learning behaviours, anomalies in the learning and teaching process, or outliers in terms of learning outcomes, often employing unsupervised or reinforcement learning approaches.

Forecasting uses past and present learning and teaching behaviours to predict future outcomes related to the process of learning and teaching, typically via supervised machine learning or knowledge-based symbolic systems.

Intelligent user interfaces support human-computer interactions across multiple media, using semi-supervised or reinforcement learning to interpret and generate content.

Goal-driven optimisation seeks the best solution to a predefined pedagogical objective.

Reasoning with knowledge structures enables systems to infer outcomes that are not explicitly present in existing data through causal reasoning and simulation.

3.4. Teacher-AI Interaction Dimension

Hybrid intelligence systems show considerable promise in advancing both theoretical frameworks and practical applications across diverse teaching contexts. For example, Holstein et al. (2020) conceptualised a hybrid complementarity framework spanning four key spaces of teacher competence: goal setting, perception, action, and decision-making. Specifically, AI can support teachers by (1) assisting in the formulation and evaluation of pedagogical goals, (2) enhancing teachers' perception of classroom situations and students' learning processes, (3) scaling pedagogical actions or task delivery, and (4) providing decision support or data-driven recommendations. This framework offers a valuable starting point for identifying target areas of teacher enhancement supported by AI and highlights the potential adaptability of AIED systems when teaming with teachers. However, it primarily conceptualises the teacher–AI combined space at a broad and largely static level, focusing on directional information flow between humans and AI while providing insufficient detail on the dynamic, fine-grained interactions and levels of control between teachers and AI. Consequently, a significant gap remains in understanding how diverse forms of teacher–AI interaction emerge and how these interactions may differentially support teacher competencies over time.

Extending the theory of distributed cognition (Hollan et al., 2000), in which cognitive processes are shared across multiple agents, hybrid intelligence can potentially emerge when human and AI agents engage in synergy. This is achieved by joining their cognitive capabilities to achieve outcomes that neither one of them could accomplish individually. Several conceptual frameworks have been proposed on how AI and teachers cooperate in educational settings to achieve hybrid intelligence. Conversely, Molenaar (2022) considers teacher-AI interactions from the aspect of the level of automation and control between teachers and AI, adapting the six levels of automation from a broader industrial and medical context to educational contexts. While this sheds light on the human-AI interactions with varying degrees of control in achieving educational tasks, such a mapping leaves limited room for understanding how AI helps develop teacher competency from a cognitive perspective and how AI learns from the interactions to further evolve. This is because the framework is strictly oriented towards task division between the teacher and AI agents, promoting productivity, as commonly prioritised in other domains, but may not necessarily align with educational goals, which are oriented towards cognitive improvement.

Cukurova (2025) posits three levels of AI integration along the spectrum of AI automation vs human control and their impacts on teacher competency in educational contexts: replacement, complementarity, and augmentation. Replacement refers to a situation where AI systems independently operate teaching tasks without, or with minimal, teacher oversight (high AI automation with low teacher control). Complementarity offers an alternative conceptualisation of AI in education, in which AI systems enhance teachers' capabilities through supportive information or operations with active control from teachers (low AI automation with high teacher control). Augmentation, on the other hand, offers a conceptualisation in which greater competence of teachers is achieved through interwoven interactions between teachers and AI (high AI automation with high teacher control). The three conceptualisations could be referred to as *complementarity levels* of teachers as affected by AI integration. Although this conceptualisation offers a concrete mapping of teacher AI interactions and their implications for teacher competence, it does not clarify how

such interactions unfold at a granular level, offering limited guidance on how teacher-AI interactions should be productively designed. Collectively, there is a need to establish a conceptual framework to systematically analyse types of interactions between teachers and AI to investigate cognitive impacts of both agents towards co-adaptation, which could potentially shape the synergistic paradigm of teacher competence development through their interactions with AI.

To address this gap, this deliverable proposes five levels of teacher–AI teaming to conceptualise different modes of teacher–AI interactions in educational contexts. Considering from the viewpoint of agentic cognitive capabilities, Crowley et al. (2022) proposes a hierarchical framework: reactive, situational, operational, praxical and creative collaboration, offering a broad concept of human and AI interactions along the dependency and complexity of collaborative AI systems. While this framework offers a promising starting point, due to its alignment with Russell and Norvig's (1995) characterisation of intelligent agents at the cognitive level, it argues for human-AI collaboration. This reflects its philosophical stance of viewing AI as a comparable agent that can collaborate with humans. The framework also lacks a strict underpinning for the educational context but instead gains inspiration from engineering contexts with an operational, output-oriented focus. Educational contexts, on the other hand, tend to focus on the cognitive improvement of agents rather than a mere focus on task completion and efficiency. We thereby adopted Crowley's framework and further appropriate it to formulate our teacher-AI interaction conceptualisation grounded in educational contexts. We choose to use the term teaming rather than collaboration, as collaboration is a well-established concept with clear definitions in research communities like computer supported collaborative learning and computer supported collaborative work (Dillenbourg, 1999) and it is not yet clear to what extent human-AI interactions can be categorised as collaboration. In this section, we describe the process of refining our framework iteratively by validating the presence of the different teaming levels identified in the literature on teacher-facing AI in education.

Fig.4 The five levels of teacher-AI teaming

The teaming levels start from minimal (transactional) teacher-AI interactions towards synergistic interactions between teachers and AI. Specifically, we propose (1) transactional, (2) situational, (3) operational, (4) praxical and (5) synergistic levels of teaming. It is worth noting that there is no hierarchical relationship between each level of teaming regarding their

effectiveness in teaching tasks. We used “levels” rather than “types” since a higher level of teaming describes a more complex way of information exchange between the teacher and the AI agent. Specifically, higher levels of teacher–AI teaming involve bidirectional, iterative, and context-sensitive exchanges in which goals, perceptions, interpretations, uncertainty, and responsibility are continuously negotiated rather than simply transmitted or acted upon. Also, a higher level of teaming usually requires more advanced AI techniques to be applied to enable such complex interaction, hence the level label can be justified. In the subsequent sections, we describe these levels in detail, supported by a teacher support application-based example to further clarify their distinctions.

3.4.1. Transactional Teaming

Transactional level entails a straightforward request-response mechanism being deployed within educational contexts where teachers instruct AI to perform a certain task autonomously following teachers’ discrete requests. In other words, a teacher provides an input command/instruction, and AI then executes and outputs a result. Transactional teaming usually happens with repetitive, minuscule, non-pedagogically-focused tasks where the task is sufficiently concrete to be automated. AI in a transactional team serves as a complete outsourcer for teachers to improve productivity, rather than enhancing the cognitive capabilities of either agents.

Fig.5 Transactional teaming. A teacher sends a request to an AI agent, and the AI agent then performs the requested action(s).

To illustrate, a teacher requests AI to translate an input text to another language for students could be perceived as a transactional teaming scenario, as the outcome of the same instruction varies very little based on background variables. For example, Srivastava and colleagues (Srivastava et al., 2021) designed an AIED system to support children with disabilities. The system can automatically transfer teachers’ instruction into texts, sign language, and Braille for students with different disabilities. In this case, teachers’ instruction was used as input and the AIED system output different forms of media as results. It helped teachers improve productivity in delivering more inclusive lessons.

3.4.2. Situational Teaming

Situational teaming refers to interactions between teachers and AI to support shared awareness of the teaching and learning context. The key differentiator of situational teaming from transactional teaming is that there is a shared state for the task that changes the agentic behaviours (may it be the human or AI agent). In essence, AI and teachers communicate to offer this state information to one another. Through this complementary information,

teachers could potentially make decisions based on a fuller understanding of the teaching and learning context.

Fig.6 Situational teaming. An AI agent gathers data from learning/teaching contexts. It then sends information to teachers. A teacher then combines their own observation with AI information to perform pedagogical decisions/actions(s).

For instance, AI systems gather contextual data from classrooms and/or learning activities retrieved from online learning systems, physical sensors or data streams, interpreting using internal models and offering educationally meaningful information to teachers. Based on AI-generated insights, teachers thereby take full agency in integrating information to make informed decisions and deliver suitable pedagogical interventions accordingly. An example of situational teaming is the Hybrid Human-Agent Tutoring (HAT) platform developed by Sawaya et al., (2025). To support instruction coaching, the HAT platform visualised behaviours of talk patterns and talk moves to the coaches and helped them with discourse practice in collaborative learning. In this case, the AIED system provided additional information about coaches’ talking behaviours during their discourse with students. Then, coaches used this information, combining it with their own experiences, to better reflect how their instruction skills can be improved.

3.4.3. Operational Teaming

Operational teaming targets task division between teachers and AI. This includes teacher-AI cooperation of plans and teaching operations deployed in teaching/learning contexts. The interaction starts when teachers provide instructions or parameters for AI systems about their goals or assigned tasks. The AI system then integrates these goals into its decision-making and adaptively acts following teachers’ requests in executing autonomous tasks or supporting teachers with goal-oriented information. This teaming extends beyond a mere task execution (happening at the transactional teaming) or reporting of situations (happening at the situational teaming) for teachers towards higher teacher control in assigning pedagogical-related goals for AI systems, aligning with teachers’ needs and enabling pedagogical-grounded task execution. For example, Yang and colleagues (2023) designed and developed an AIED system to support the orchestration of dynamic transitions between individual and collaborative learning. The AIED system provided suggestions for grouping the students based on the different grouping strategies set by human teachers.

Fig.7 Operational teaming. A teacher sets a goal(s) for an AI agent in terms of tasks, action plans or parameters, and the AI agent then performs the requested action(s) according to the teacher’s instructions.

3.4.4. Praxical Teaming

Praxical teaming emphasises that teachers and AI systems dynamically exchange information on teaching and learning procedures, actions, or plans towards establishing a shared understanding and effective practice. This means that the agents can learn from each other to change their behaviours to optimise the collective system over time.

Fig.8 Praxical teaming. An AI agent provides feedback/information about learning/teaching contexts to a teacher. The teacher reviews and revises the feedback. The AI agent then incorporates the teacher’s inputs to produce new feedback. The teacher and the AI agent can engage in this iterative reviewing and revising process until the teacher is satisfied with the feedback before they take actions.

While teachers activate their prior experience and professional expertise during praxical teaming, AI systems incorporate learning patterns or information queried from databases to tackle specific tasks/questions at hand. Essentially, AI systems can learn from teacher feedback (implicit, such as choices, preferences, and explicit, such as liking, rating, etc.) by updating their model and adapting to teachers’ pedagogical guidance or preferences in the long term. For example, Bernius and colleagues (2021) proposed a machine learning approach for suggesting feedback in textual exercise in large courses. The approach was integrated into an AIED system and used by 53 teachers in two courses. The system can initially generate feedback for students’ textual exercises. Then, teachers can choose to accept,

extend, or change the initial feedback. Based on teachers' inputs, the AIED system learns from them and generates feedback that is more aligned with teachers' needs in the next iterations.

3.4.5. Synergistic Teaming

Synergistic teaming happens when teachers and an AI system maintain their agency while mutually engaged in co-adaptation. In contrast to praxical teaming, the AI system operated at synergistic teaming should not only be able to blindly follow teachers' instructions (operational teaming) and adapt to teacher feedback (praxical teaming), but also be able to critically engage in evaluating teacher feedback, reason with logic and evidence, 'push back' or offer a gentle nudge when teacher feedback is mismatched and be ready to accept and adapt when evaluation is congruent. This teaming requires high agency from both teachers and AI systems to critically engage and push the boundaries of one another, along with dynamic and sustained communication between both agents towards synergy. When this teaming is achieved, it forms creative resonance and enables teachers and AI systems to deepen task understanding and potentially generate innovative outcomes that individuals could not achieve alone (Cukurova, 2025), signifying the potential synergistic augmentation of teacher competence towards hybrid competence. In comparison to synergistic teaming, praxical teaming relies on teachers' current competence to give feedback to AI. With a high reliance on teacher feedback, the combined competence of both agents often saturates at the maximum competence of teachers, leaving little or no improvement beyond their current practices. On the other hand, synergistic teaming supports mutual adaptation from both teachers and AI. With teachers' pedagogical goals introduced by the teacher and AI's capacity to carry out complex tasks and to learn, synergistic teaming is theoretically possible, yet difficult to achieve in real-world practice. This difficulty is partly due to the substantial resource costs required to develop and support sufficiently adaptive AI systems, as well as the significant time and effort demanded of teachers to engage in these complex interactions.

Fig.9 The synergistic teaming. Similar to the praxical level, an AI agent provides feedback/information about learning/teaching contexts to a teacher. The teacher reviews and revises the feedback. Rather than the AI agent obediently incorporating the teacher's inputs to revise feedback, the AI agent will critically engage in challenging the ideas of teachers by providing counter opinions. Both agents iteratively negotiate until reaching a consensus.

Fig.10 A detailed visualisation of the TAICo Teacher-facing AI Taxonomy

4. Systematic Literature Review

In order to have a comprehensive understanding of the cutting-edge AI tools used by teachers in practice, a systematic literature review was conducted in T3.1 to analyse the teacher-facing AI in the previous literature using characteristics identified in the AI taxonomy presented above.

Through an inspection of existing literature reviews in AI for education (see Appendix 1), they tend to offer a narrow scope of the analysis, such as focusing on a particular educational level (such as K-12, as in Murphy (2019); Topali et al.(2025) or higher education as in Sarwari, (2024), a specific learning context (such as language learning, as in (Ali, 2020), or a specific AI application (such as ChatGPT, as in Baidoo-Anu & Ansah (2023); chatbots as in Labadze et al. (2023); AI-based robots as in (Malik & Shah, 2025). While some reviews were not confined to AI applications for teachers, they focus on examining AI applications in supporting teacher professional development (e.g. Jamal, 2023; Salas-Pilco et al., 2022). As this group of reviews positions teachers as learners in the context, it focuses on the benefits of AI for training teachers to improve their teaching profession and ignores the potential of AI tools in actual teaching practices. Other reviews are primarily oriented towards task-focused applications for teachers (such as Gentile et al., 2023; Humble & Mozelius, 2019; Jamal, 2023; Lamas & Arnab, 2022), omitting technical affordances and interaction analysis between teachers and AI to realise their impacts on teacher competency development. For example, Humble & Mozelius (2019) synthesise how teachers support AI vs how AI supports teachers, lacking granularity of teacher-AI interactions at the cognitive levels. Reviews by Gentile et al. (2023) and Jamal (2023) primarily examined the evolving roles of teachers in the AI era, seeking potential benefits and concerns of AI rather than on how these changes manifest through teacher-AI interactions.

Therefore, this review aims to conduct a systematic literature review to reflect the current landscape of teacher-facing AI tools through the proposed teacher-facing AI taxonomy. The review focuses on empirical studies that examine AI-supported teaching tasks across educational levels, with particular attention to those that explicitly describe teacher-AI interactions. By analysing these interactions practically through a concrete technological lens, the review serves three main objectives: to investigate prerequisite conditions on technical capabilities that afford varying levels of teaming, to realise teaming interactions that are present in the current landscape of AI and its empirical impacts on the teacher-AI complementarity space, and to identify ethical and practical factors beyond technical development, nurturing fruitful adoption of AI supported teaching and sustainable growth of teacher profession.

RQ1 AI Techniques: What types of AI technologies are used and deployed to support teaching tasks in empirical studies (i.e. teacher-facing AI)?

This RQ aims to explore types of AI tools that are currently used to support teaching tasks. While there are AIED reviews presented (e.g., Holmes & Tuomi, 2022), most of them only focused on classifying broad applications of AI in educational contexts (e.g., assessment for teachers) and crude levels of AI models used for AIED. This overlooks the nuanced ways in which AI tools interact with teachers in practice. Specifically, these taxonomies lack detailed

characteristics of AI tools that may nurture or hinder the technical capabilities of AIED. Specifically, these literature reviews lack detailed characteristics of AI tools that may nurture or hinder the technical capabilities of teacher-facing AI. Therefore, this review aims to capture technical specifications of AI tools, reflecting the current landscape of teacher-facing AI tools. This review adopts the characteristics from the AI Agent Characterisation Dimension in the AI taxonomy presented above, to guide the understanding of the AI agents' technical features, particularly on their potential to facilitate or hinder teacher capabilities through teacher-AI interactions.

RQ2 Interactions: What are the levels of teacher-AI teaming in empirical studies of teacher-facing AI?

Teacher agency plays a crucial role in both harnessing the strengths of educational AI systems and addressing related ethical concerns. Examining how teachers interact with AIED systems provides an important lens for understanding their agency. This review thereby categorises teacher-AI interactions proposed in the studies to the teaming levels proposed in the AI taxonomy and examines whether the lower level of teaming with limited teachers' oversight may be linked to higher replacement of teachers' agency. Conversely, the higher levels of teaming may hypothetically promote teachers' complementarity and augmentation. This exploration could elucidate the relationship between teacher-AI teaming and complementarity levels, reflecting interaction conditions and design principles of interactions to positively support complementarity and augmentation.

RQ3 Context: How are teacher-facing AI tools designed, developed and deployed in empirical studies?

Beyond types of AI technologies, this review seeks to understand the design, development and deployment context of teacher-facing AI tools. Existing reviews tend to consider AI tools as static products, overlooking their socio-technological paradigms underpinning the effectiveness of the teacher-facing AI tools, particularly on how these tools are developed and implemented. This may obscure other important contextual factors that may affect teacher adoption of such tools in actual teaching/learning contexts, such as a lack of human-centred design principles or limited guidance provided for teachers. This review thereby foregrounds contextual factors, investigating conditions for/against support teacher-AI tools.

RQ4 Impacts: What are the observed impacts of teacher-facing AI tools on the dependent variables measured?

This review investigated the reported impacts of the AI tools in the empirical studies. Measured outcomes (e.g., changes in behaviours, perceived usefulness), means of measurements (e.g., self-report measures, actual teaching/learning changes), and means of analysis and report are considered factors representing the impacts of the current state-of-the-art teacher-facing AI tools in education. Several stakeholders, mainly targeted teachers and learners, are all recorded to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impacts. Through documentation, this review seeks to present a synthesis of evidence reported in teacher-facing AI research, offering an overview of the academic landscape of the

effectiveness of AI tools for teachers and potentially highlighting teacher-AI teaming levels and contextual factors that may mediate these effects.

4.1. Methodology

This work adopted the systematic literature review guidelines proposed by Kitchenham & Charters (2007) due to their widespread use and applicability in the learning analytics (LA) and AIED fields (e.g., Topali et al., 2025; Villa-Torrano et al., 2023). The guidelines comprise three overarching phases: (1) research planning, (2) review execution involving information extraction and synthesis, and (3) dissemination of results.

During the planning phase, Web of Science (WoS) was selected as the sole database for this study because of its relevance and comprehensive coverage of major journals and influential conferences in the LA and AIED fields. Given that AIED is a fast-growing domain with a high volume of publications each year, WoS was also chosen for practical reasons related to manageability. After selecting the database, search strings were constructed using keywords that captured technical aspects (e.g., AI), target users (e.g., teacher), and educational contexts (e.g., education) (see Table 1). Notably, neither teacher-facing AI nor complementarity was explicitly included, as these terms were not commonly used based on observations from pilot searches. The search was restricted to titles, abstracts, and metadata (excluding full texts), while no disciplinary field restrictions were applied in order to include studies from interdisciplinary domains (e.g., computer science and education). The publication period was constrained from 2010 to August 2025, aligning with a period of significant transformation in AI driven by advances in computing power and data availability. After removing duplicates, the initial keyword search yielded 561 candidate papers.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria used to scope the review are presented in Table 2. This review focuses exclusively on empirical studies published in peer-reviewed journals or conference proceedings, written in English, and exceeding six pages in length. Only studies that deployed AI systems for teachers (i.e., teacher-facing AI) and explicitly described teacher–AI interactions were included. For example, studies deploying intelligent tutoring systems (ITSs) for students, while noting potential benefits for reducing teacher workload, were excluded if no direct teacher–AI interaction was reported. Studies were also excluded if teachers participated only in research-related activities (e.g., providing data for model training or evaluating AI outputs) without directly engaging with the AI tools, as such studies lacked essential information on design affordances and interaction mechanisms. Empirical studies that did not specify concrete teaching tasks (e.g., surveys examining teachers’ perceptions of using ChatGPT for language learning) were likewise excluded. Similarly, studies that did not clearly specify the AI tools involved were excluded due to insufficient detail regarding technological mechanisms and interactions (e.g., studies broadly evaluating teachers’ use of AI tools such as Grammarly or QuillBot for language education). Finally, studies focusing on AI tools for in-service teacher professional development were excluded, as teachers primarily acted as learners in training contexts rather than using AI to directly support teaching tasks.

Table 1. Search keywords

<p>Search terms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological aspect (topic only): (“AI” OR “Artificial intelligence” OR “personalized learning” OR “intelligent tutoring system” OR “adaptive system” OR “expert tutoring system” OR “deep learning” OR “neural network” OR “natural language processing” OR “GPT*” OR “LLM*” OR “intelligent virtual reality” OR “chatbot” OR “machine learning” OR “automated tutor*” OR “intelligent agent*”) AND • User (topic only): (“teacher*” OR “instructor*”) AND • NOT: (“literature review” OR “systematic review” OR “special issue” OR “chapter”) • Context: (“k-12” OR “school*” OR “education” OR “kindergarten” OR “pre school” OR “early childhood” OR “universit*” OR “college*” OR “online learning” OR “lifelong learning” OR “postgraduate*” OR “undergraduate*” OR “classroom*” OR “class” OR “course*” OR “learner*” OR “e-learning” OR “hybrid learning” OR “blended learning” OR “remote learning” OR “game-based learning” OR “learning process*” OR “learning performance” OR “learning environment*” OR “learning outcome*” OR “lecture*” OR “pedagog*” OR “apprentic*” OR “didactic*”) • PUBLISHED from year 2010-2025
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Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

<p>Inclusion Criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-reviewed empirical studies • Published from the year 2010 onwards • Reported in English • Studies involving AI tools or systems to support teachers (teacher-facing AI) in their teaching tasks. <p>Exclusion Criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conceptual, theoretical, opinion or short papers without empirical data • Studies on AI tools or systems with no feedback/interactions with teachers • Studies not focused on specific teaching tasks • Studies that engage in-service teachers as students in the context • Studies with missing key information
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During the execution phase, two researchers conducted the title and abstract screening using the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. To ensure screening consistency, interrater reliability was calculated on the first 10% of the records, yielding a Cohen’s kappa of 0.82, which indicates medium-to-high agreement. After resolving disagreements through discussion, the two researchers independently screened the remaining records. This title-abstract screening stage resulted in 561 papers. Next, four researchers participated in the full-text screening. They initially coded three papers and jointly discussed discrepancies to establish a shared understanding of the coding scheme. Additional papers were then included in iterative cycles of independent coding followed by group discussion. Subsequently, 10% of the records were double-coded by the four researchers, resulting in a Krippendorff’s alpha of 0.69, indicating moderate agreement. The remaining papers were then coded independently by the four researchers.

Based on the initial pool of papers included after full-text screening, forward and backward snowballing, operationalised following (Gauthier et al., 2022), was conducted to identify potentially relevant studies that were not captured in the initial database search. Applying the same procedures of title-abstract screening, full-text review, and data extraction, a total of 103 papers were included in the final dataset. Figure 11 summarises the review protocol and the corresponding number of papers at each stage.

Fig.11 The review protocol and the corresponding number of papers.

For the coding process, characteristics derived from the TAICo teacher-facing AI taxonomy were used to develop the coding scheme for the first two research questions, which primarily focused on the AI technique dimension and the interaction dimension. For each specific teaching task identified in the reviewed papers, we extracted descriptions of interactions between teachers and the AI system and mapped them onto the five levels of teacher–AI teaming. For the remaining components of the coding scheme, a deductive approach was predominantly employed for data extraction. Specifically, predefined codes drawn from the literature were used to situate the findings within established frameworks, ensuring a systematic approach to capturing recurring patterns across empirical studies. Inductive coding was applied when existing themes were insufficient, resulting in the creation of new codes.

Appendix 2 summarises the literature and frameworks that informed the coding scheme in relation to the research questions. Because a single paper may report on more than one empirical study, the researchers agreed to document each study that included reported teacher–AI interactions. In cases where multiple AI models were described within a study, the dominant model was coded in detail, with supplementary notes recorded for other models to support further analysis. In some instances, descriptions of the AI system were not provided in the same paper in which the evaluation was conducted. When traceable references to AI specifications were available, the researchers consulted these sources to obtain the necessary technical information. Conversely, studies that lacked sufficient AI-related detail were marked as missing key information and excluded from the review.

The final annotated set of included papers is made available via an online repository¹. Descriptive statistics, visualisations, and illustrative examples are presented in the Results section, in alignment with the research questions.

¹ https://osf.io/2n6wy/overview?view_only=e1d067b8d9c648ccb75951f10ea5a08f

4.2. What types of AI technologies are used

This section summarises the technological characteristics of teacher-facing AI tools used in empirical studies. We summarise how teacher-facing AI tools were leveraged by considering the agent type, the model type, information about the data input and output, the evolution capability of the model, the tasks of the AI agents, and the interface provided for the end users.

Agent Type

First, when conceptualising AI used to support teachers in empirical papers as agents, model-based agents emerge as the most prominent agent type found in empirical studies of teacher-facing AI tools, representing 43.7% of the total. To illustrate, Bayesian networks are used as model-based agents to classify students' focus and attention in classrooms (e.g. Chiu & Tseng, 2021). Goal-based and utility-based agents are commonly reported, accounting for 34% and 13.6% of the systems, respectively. While a goal-based agent operates by selecting actions to achieving goals, e.g., the GPT3 model used in tailoring affective-motivational feedback aligned with students' data (Sung et al., 2025), a utility agent evaluate and select actions that maximise a utility function towards goals, e.g., GPT4o was used in conjunction with teachers' selected parameters to optimise lesson plans according to their preferences (Faraji et al., 2025). Notably, simple reflex agents are less frequently observed, contributing to 8.7% of the total. For example, Popescu & Badica (2011) deployed a simple reflex agent as rule-based metadata defined by teachers to govern content delivery for students. However, learning agents are notably absent from the empirical studies reviewed, signifying a gap in the field, particularly regarding AI systems that are capable of autonomously improving themselves to better support teaching tasks.

Fig.12 The proportion of agent types identified in empirical studies

Model Information

When examining types of models used in teacher-facing AI tools from their knowledge representation and reasoning style, there is a balanced proportion between hybrid models (49.5%) and statistical models (40.8%). Symbolic models were minimally utilised, appearing in 8.7% of the empirical studies. According to OECD (2022), statistical AI models rely mainly on patterns identified from data, while symbolic AI models utilise expert knowledge to create logical reasoning for inferences. For example, Amir & Gal (2013) created expert rules conceptualising how chemistry problems should be solved and used greedy algorithms on log data to create hierarchical trees of how students actually solve the problems. Hybrid AI models combine both statistical and symbolic approaches. Generative AI also falls under this category, where rules were set in addition to models built on existing patterns learned from data. This pattern reflects advances in the field where data was mainly used as a source of model beyond expert-crafted knowledge.

Fig.13 The variation of AI algorithms (%) used in empirical studies

Apart from knowledge sources of the models, we also considered from a technical machine learning model perspective, as outlined by Mukhamediev et al. (2021), reflecting their learning paradigms and architectures used. Deep learning (51.2%) and supervised machine learning (38.6%) collectively represent almost 90% of the total models used in supporting teaching tasks. In contrast, unsupervised learning (8.4%), reinforcement learning (3.1%) and semi-supervised learning (1.1%) represent only a minor proportion of the AI tools. Despite the evolutionary capabilities of reinforcement models, they were utilised in only three studies, reflecting limitations in the current landscape in which AI could be leveraged to improve outcomes based on teachers' feedback. To illustrate, Williams et al., (2018) developed a MOOC plugin called DynamicProblem to support teachers in experimenting with variations of textual feedback explaining correct answers for students' closed-ended answers. After teachers initially set up different textual elaboration messages with their confidential

level for feedback variants, the Dynamic Problem employed a multi-armed bandit reinforcement approach, specifically Thompson sampling with Bayesian inference, to optimise feedback variants for each student based on prior students’ ratings of feedback helpfulness and report a probabilistic summary for teachers. With a significant proportion of the teacher-facing AI tools using generative AI (39%), advanced techniques for LLMs were further explored. Prompt engineering represents the pervasive techniques deployed in teaching contexts (77.5%), whereas other advanced techniques (e.g., in-context learning, RAG, Retrieval-Augmented Generation, or SLHF, Supervised Learning from Human Feedback) are somewhat limited (7.5%). One of the minority studies that deployed advanced techniques, such as in-context learning, is from Tang et al. (2024). They developed a Generative AI system named VizGroup, aiming to help teachers orchestrate the collaborative learning programming module. To achieve this, a few-shot prompting, covering input and output examples, was used to enhance the model’s accuracy in correctly identifying group ranking based on its seriousness and alerting such information to teachers. Despite advanced techniques for enhancing generative AI’s technical capabilities, their limited utilisation highlights a gap in implementing those approaches, particularly at the model inference phase for promoting model adaptation towards teachers’ pedagogical goals.

Examining the technical affordances of the AI models supporting agent types, Fig. 14 indicates that as types of agents progress from simple reflex agents to utility-based agents, the AI models are more sophisticated, leaning towards the use of deep neural networks. Simple reflex and model-based agents relied heavily upon supervised learning models, while goal-based and utility-based agents tend to rely upon deep learning models.

Fig.14 The relationship between algorithms used and agent types identified in the empirical studies

Data Information

In terms of the data perspective, most data were **collected from students** (69.9%) and from teachers (42.7%), mainly through digital learning environments. A small number of studies utilised other data sources coming from external (3.9%) and physical learning environments (1.9%). In terms of **data modality**, not to our surprise, textual and log data represented the largest proportion, accounting for 50.5% and 46.6%, respectively. Audio and video are the following modalities, with the proportion of 14.6% and 11.7%, respectively. Other modalities include ratings (7.8%), physiological data (3.9%), images (3.9%) and sensors (2.9%). To illustrate, Deng & Rattadilok, (2022) obtained environmental and physiological data captured from sensors of Arduino and Apple Watch, respectively, to identify students' distractions and anxiety and offer such information on students' conditions as well as their potential causes to teachers.

Model Evolution

While the models used, including supervised learning models and generative AI models, hold the capabilities to update their parameters, most of the studies deployed static models with no evolution (82.5%). On the contrary, the evolving models were only found in 11.7% and 5.8% of the studies through active interactions with teachers or passive interactions with AI, respectively. Model evolution with active interactions refers to models that can incorporate knowledge from user interactions to update their parameters for more accurate or effective results, such as a recommendation system in Pereira et al. (2023)'s study. The model assists computer science teachers by recommending similar programming problems to the target problem. As the model offers the results for teachers, teachers can teach the model about its misclassification of topics, leading to updating its knowledge and correcting the model for future recommendations. On the other hand, model evolution with passive interactions refers to the models that connect to updated data streams, adapting new inputs automatically. (Herodotou et al., 2019), for instance, allowed the predictive model for identifying at-risk students to incorporate new knowledge regarding students' online activities into the model to simultaneously update its prediction. Both approaches are crucial to contribute to model improvement. While models' passive interactions reflect no teacher control over how the model improves, active interactions, instead, autonomously steer the model towards teachers' goals.

Model Evolution

Fig.15 The proportion of model evolutionary capabilities reported in the empirical studies

AI Tasks

In terms of AI processes, most empirical studies used AI for recognition tasks (45.6%), followed by communicating through an intelligent interface (38.8%) for fostering interactive interactions. Other processes include event detection (14.6%), forecasting (12.6%), personalisation (5.8%), goal-driven optimisation (5.8%) and reasoning with knowledge structure (3.9%). Through these AI processes, AI tools were used to derive target constructs. Unsurprisingly, AI tools primarily targeted students' learning outcomes inference, including their knowledge and skills (44.7%), followed by authorising learning materials (28.2%), identifying students' online learning processes (23.3%), and synthesising information from the learning environment to develop teacher awareness (15.5%). To illustrate, AI targets enhancing teacher awareness by obtaining classroom information to analyse teaching practice and then offer insights such as teachers' uses of focused questions (Demszky et al., 2025). Considering their non-mutually exclusive dimensions of target construct in relation to stakeholders (Table 3), without surprise, the cognitive dimension is the focus of the AI tools, accounting for 35.9% and 25.2% for learners and teachers, respectively. Metacognition is the second largest proportion of construct dimensions, representing 7.8% in learners and 9.7% in teachers. Teachers' affects (1.9%), motivation (1.9%) and sociocultural (1.9%) dimensions are largely overlooked by the empirical studies. It is noted that there are also considerable amount of studies with no specific target constructs (37.9%), particularly for those using general purpose generative AI for learning material generation, such as in Elkins et al., (2024) where GPT3.5 was used to generate questions corresponding to the input texts.

Table 3 The percentages of target construct dimensions (columns) per stakeholder group (rows) identified in the empirical studies, which are non-mutually exclusive.

Stakeholder	Affect	Cognition	Metacognition	Motivation	Sociocultural	Others
Learners	9.7%	35.9%	7.8%	5.8%	2.9%	37.9%
Teachers	1.9%	25.2%	9.7%	1.9%	1.9%	

Interface

With derived information, outputs were predominantly delivered to teachers after the teaching period (49.5%), with the remaining AI outputs delivered before (34%) and during (34%) teaching periods. This sheds light on the increasing potential of AI tools to be used in real-time during classes. A dashboard comprising visualisations and texts emerged as the most common interface for interacting with AI outputs (65%), followed by chatbots (25.2%) and textual feedback (19.4%). Other interfaces, including immersive devices (5.8%) such as augmented glasses for teachers (Holstein et al., 2018) and speech agents (1%), remain limited areas of study.

4.3. Teacher-AI Teaming and Complementarity Levels

In addition to the technical capabilities of the AI systems, the interaction dimension was also investigated. As described above in detail, extending Crowley et al., (2022)'s human-AI collaboration framework, we proposed five levels of teacher-AI teaming: transactional, situational, operational, praxical and synergistic teaming in our AI taxonomy. We found that 45.6% of teacher-AI interactions in the empirical studies can be categorised predominantly at the situational level, followed by the operational level (31.1%) and the transactional level (19.4%). Praxical teaming is rarely found, with only 3.9% whereas none of the AI would sufficiently satisfy the level of synergistic teaming that we proposed. Specifically, at the transactional level, teachers interact with AI systems in a request-response manner with little control over the system. For instance, teachers instructed the GPT model to analyse students' virtual-lab sequences in comparison to their sequences, offering automated experimental step correction for students (Machado et al., 2025).

At the situational teaming, AI helps teachers gather situational information and supply such information to them, supporting their situational awareness. Teachers thereby have high control in performing subsequent pedagogical interventions themselves. Lin et al. (2025) leveraged GPT-4 to detect important keywords from students' group discussion in STEM subjects and offer a summary through real-time dashboard for teachers. They then utilise this situational-specific information to administer appropriate intervention accordingly.

Operational teaming, on the other hand, targets interactions between teachers and AI where teachers assign specific goals or set parameters for the AI systems to meaningfully perform tasks, suggesting higher control of teachers in instructing AI operations according to their pedagogical goals within the teaching and learning contexts. A study by Choi et al., (2024) is one of the examples of operational teaming where teachers can author student-AI dialogues

according to their pedagogical goals. At first, teachers upload a lecture video to the system and identify common areas of struggles in the lecture transcript to generate dialogue scenarios for student practice. With initial AI suggestions on dialogue scenarios based on teachers' selected content, teachers can select dialogue scenarios to review and refine at the utterance levels before implementing them.

Praxical teaming represents teachers' authority in revising AI outputs along with AI learning capabilities to incorporate teachers' feedback to improve the model. Pereira et al. (2023) illustrate praxical teaming by enabling the AI models to learn teachers' feedback preferences over time for improving its recommendation model. Situated in the programming context, teachers select a target programming problem. The AI model then recommends an equivalent problem for teachers to review. Teachers can accept or reject the recommended problem with a rejection reason. If the recommended problem was rejected due to incorrect topic classification, the model learns the correct topics towards better recommendation, supporting praxical teaming.

However, none of the studies were found to operate at synergistic teaming. Synergistic teaming refers to teacher-AI interactions beyond praxical levels where AI not only learns from teachers' feedback but starts pushing back on the teachers' ideas based on its goals. This reflects teacher-AI interactive and mutual exchanges for co-reasoning to reach shared decisions between the two agents, which could ideally support teacher-AI synergy. A lack of synergistic teaming studies in this review will be further discussed in Section 5.

To understand technical affordances supporting interaction affordances, we explore the prerequisite technical capabilities of the AI systems from the agent perspective that support each teaming level. Table 4 summarises emerging patterns of AI agents along teaming levels. From the empirical data, multiple types of agents were utilised at the transactional level whereas at the situational level, only model- and goal-based agents were found. For operational teaming, goal- and utility-based agents emerged with utility-based agents supporting the praxical teaming. These patterns somewhat suggest the minimum technical requirements for each teaming level, where higher levels of teaming are conditioned on higher levels of agents.

Table.4 The relationship between agent types (row) and teaming levels (column) identified in the empirical studies (%)

Agent types	1. Transactional	2. Situational	3. Operational	4. Praxical
1. Simple reflex agent	8.74%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
2. Model-based agent	2.91%	40.78%	0.00%	0.00%
3. Goal-based agent	6.80%	4.85%	22.33%	0.00%
4. Utility-based agent	0.97%	0.00%	8.74%	3.88%

Regarding the three levels of complementarity (replacement, complement and augmentation) conceptualised by Cukurova, (2025), the majority of the AI used was found at the complement levels (88.3%), with the minority of the studies categorised as replacement (10.7%). Only one study(Liu et al., 2024a) was categorised as augmentation, presenting evidence of synergy that the combination of AI and teachers could achieve synergy with performance greater than any of the agents could achieve alone. Fig 16 represents a relationship between teaming levels and the levels of complementarity. Among papers coded as replacement (n=11), only the transactional (72.2%) and operational teaming (27.3%) were identified. This aligned with the automated nature of the operation, where AI was either to perform a request at the transactional level or perform distributed tasks following goals assigned by teachers at the operational levels. On the contrary, the complement level (n=91) was identified across teaming levels ranging from the simple transactional (8.7%), situational (50.5%), operational (31.9%) to praxical level (4.4%), with one augmented level (n=1) coded at the situational level. This partly suggested that AI; while having the potential to replace humans according to its capabilities to automate at the transactional and operational levels, it also has the potential to both complement and augment. It is acknowledged that due to the scope of the papers focused on teacher-AI interactions and the empirical evidence reported in academic journals/conferences serving as the standard for this systematic literature review, this review might fall short in covering the actual amount of replacement in education where no teacher interaction was not presented in the article. The research might be categorised at the complement level, rather than augment, due to the lack of evidence to sufficiently supply the three conditions: teacher + AI, AI-only and teacher-only.

Fig.16 The relationship between teaming levels (left) and complementarity levels (right) as identified in the empirical studies

4.4. Design, Deployment and Development Factors

Beyond the technical capabilities, the design, development and deployment factors that potentially affect the effectiveness of teacher-facing AI tools were explored. Regarding the **teaching tasks**, teacher-facing AI tools were designed and deployed to support teachers across the teaching cycle from conceptualisation, authoring, implementation, regulation, evaluation, and reflection phases. With the major proportion of AI systems to support teachers in authoring teaching and learning materials (32%), monitoring real-time ongoing learning activities and assessing learning outcomes are the next most common applications of AI, with the proportion of 28.2% and 27.2%, respectively. AI could be used by teachers to conceptualise learning needs (as in Romero et al., 2013), authoring teaching and learning materials (as in Bai et al., 2024), regulating classrooms through real-time monitoring of students' learning activities (as in Han et al., 2021) or automatically evaluating learning outcomes such as mathematics problems (as in Liu et al., 2024).

From Fig. 17, empirical studies reveal that the teaming levels emerged across teaching phases. Transactional teaming happened equally across teaching phases, with a lower proportion at the conceptualisation phase. Situational teaming mainly happened at the regulation (e.g., monitoring ongoing learning activities) and evaluation phases (e.g. assessing learning outcomes). Operational teaming happens mostly at the authoring (e.g. designating teaching and learning materials) and conceptualisation phase (e.g. identifying learning needs and learning goals) while praxical teaming expands across the conceptualisation, implementation and evaluation phases. This provides emerging evidence that teaching phases are not exclusively associated with particular teaming levels. Despite the hierarchical framing of teaming levels, reflecting higher cognitive exchange and shared decision-making between teachers and AI, the appropriate teaming level should be aligned with teachers' goals or the task at hand.

Fig.17 The relationship between teaming levels (left) and teaching tasks (right) as identified in the empirical studies.

Considering the deployment context of the AI tools, higher **education** is the prominent studied context, accounting for 39.8%, followed by secondary (28.2%), and primary education (19.4%). Surprisingly, the **countries** where the studies were conducted were unidentified for 25.2% of the total. Among the reported countries, there is a significant proportion of studies conducted in the United States (19.4%), followed by China (10.7%), and other countries accounted for 44.8%. In terms of **subjects**, 59.2% of the empirical studies are conducted in the STEM fields, followed by art, humanities and social science (25.2%), while 16.5% of the studies have unidentified subjects. Notable **instructional strategies**, in ascending order of prevalence, include interactive learning (31.1%), such as collaborative learning, peer learning; individualised learning (29.1%), such as drill-down practices; instructor-centred learning (16.5%), such as lecture; and experiential learning (13.6%). 22.3% of the studies showed unspecified instruction. While over one-third of the studies did not report their **mode of delivery** (35.9%), the remaining studies delivered instruction online (28.2%), face-to-face (25.2%), blended (10.7%) or hybrid (1.9%).

Considering the **ecological validity** of the studies, it was surprising that most of the studies were implemented in real-world/authentic contexts, accounting for 38.8%. A comparable proportion of studies (37.9%) was conducted in lab-based settings, with another 23.3% were carried out in near real-world contexts, representing a transitional stage that introduces real-world complexities within a simulated environment. In terms of **technology readiness**, over 70% of the AI tools in the studies achieved the technology readiness levels of 4 to 6, demonstrating viable technological solutions implemented and validated in relevant environments. Among these, 11.7% used well-established AI systems with a technology readiness level of 9, meaning operational systems deployed in real-world, large-scale platforms, such as ChatGPT (Asadi et al., 2025; Han & Li, 2024) and a web-based class report platform for teachers named TeachFX (Demszky et al., 2025). Unsurprisingly, nearly half of the studies (49.5%) deployed their own AI tools, considering them as academic/personal AI solutions, while 35.9% did not provide sufficient information to determine the **business models** of the AI tools being implemented. 11.7% deployed commercial solutions, with only 2.9% reported using non-profit AI tools.

In the AI **design process**, over 70% of the studies reveal concerning findings that no stakeholders were involved. Among the remaining, 27.2% explicitly included teachers in the design process, followed by other stakeholders such as students (3.9%), educational experts (1.9%), technical experts (1%) and staff (1%). When AI was introduced into the context, nearly 60% of the studies lacked a report on any **onboarding or technical support**, potentially leaving teachers to self-explore the tools. Only one-third (35.9%) of the studies offered initial training sessions for teachers, followed by a marginal proportion of 6.8% and 5.8% that provided ongoing support and self-studied materials, respectively. Surprisingly, **ethical considerations of the AI systems** were rarely reported across the AI's design, development and deployment phases, accounting for less than 10% of the studies (Fig 18). Human-centred design and teacher autonomy are the main ethical issues considered in the design/development (6.8%) and the deployment phases (6.8%), followed by privacy (3.9%) and transparency and accountability (3.9%) issues noted during the deployment phase. One of the approaches that a human-centred design study used is conducting workshops with educational experts and teachers in developing guidelines to inform design features of the AI systems (Choi et al., 2024). It is worth noting that these recorded ethical considerations pertain only to AI systems themselves, rather than to the research perspectives.

Fig.18 The relationship between the proportion of empirical studies reporting an ethical dimension (columns) and the corresponding development phases (rows).

4.5. Impacts of Teacher-facing AI

In realising the effectiveness of teacher-facing AI tools, we examined how the empirical studies reported evidence of their impact. Over half of the studies were conducted in a single session (57.3%), suggesting the novelty of the tools being introduced into the teaching context. A notable amount of the studies (20.4%) was conducted in a long-term period with over 10 weeks. In terms of the frequency of the AI tools used by teachers, almost half of the studies (44.7%) did not explicitly specify the frequency. Of the remaining studies, 43.7% reported that teachers only engaged with the tools once, likely during an introductory session in which they were familiarised with the tool and engaged with it for research purposes.

Fig.19 The proportion of evaluation study duration (left) and the frequency of teacher engagement with the AI tools in the studies (right)

These studies measured from both teachers' and learners' perspectives, with the prominent trend in measuring teachers' perceived usefulness (48.5%), followed by the usability (36.9%), impacts on teaching (33%), such as the teaching strategies adopted when

teachers interacted with situational dashboards (Sawaya & D’Mello, 2025) and changes in behaviours before and after engaging with AI tools (30.1%), such as a 60% increase in the use of uptake strategies, as suggested by AI tools (Demszky et al., 2025). From learners’ perspectives, impacts on learning (26.2%), such as students’ pre/post knowledge test in basic programming (Lin et al., 2024) and changes in their behaviours (14.6%).

To determine such constructs, several data sources and techniques were collected from research, as in Figure 21. Self-reported measures appear as the dominant data sources collected to evaluate the impacts of the studies. While interviews, focus groups and think-aloud approaches with qualitative analysis account for 45.6% of the total studies, self-reported questionnaires with descriptive statistics are primarily used in 42.7% of the studies. Experimental conditions were implemented in nearly one-third of the studies with a combination of descriptive (27.2%) and inferential (28.2%) statistics. Only a small proportion of studies (7.8%-13.6%) consider deploying observation and objective measures, such as logs or artefacts, to observe the impacts of teacher-facing AI tools.

Fig.20 The relationship between empirical measurements (column) and educational stakeholders (row) expressed as percentages.

When considering the experimental studies (n=39, 37.9%), we found that students surprisingly emerged as the top target participants, accounting for 61.5%, exceeding the proportion of teachers (46.2%). Majority of the studies that implemented teacher-facing AI tools with experimental conditions evaluated the impacts of their interventions through students’ performance (such as in Jia & Miao, 2021; Li et al., 2023; Rafique et al., 2021); or perceptions including their motivation (such as in Bai et al., 2024) and self-efficacy (e.g., You et al., 2019), rather than any evaluation of the teacher performance and/or competence. On the other hand, experimental studies that evaluated teacher-related measures, those measures target teachers’ self-reported perceptions (System Usability Scale (SUS) (Bangor et al., 2008) in (Demszky et al., 2025; Deng & Rattadilok, 2022; Faraji et al., 2025), workload (such as NASA-TLX questionnaire (Hart & Staveland, 1988) as in (Faraji et al., 2025; Jin et al., 2025), behavioural engagement from log data such as the number of using generation button or modify the question attributes, (Kang et al., 2025), a tracking of whether a teacher opened the focusing questions email and whether they viewed the focusing question, (Demszky et al., 2025) and performance, including task completion scores (Paiva & Bittencourt, 2020), quality

of quiz (Elkins et al., 2024), quality of lesson plans (Fan et al., 2024), grading performance (Xiao et al., 2025), or perceived levels of situation awareness (as measured through Situation Awareness Global Assessment Technique (SAGAT) questionnaire (Jane, 2019) in (Kasempalu et al., 2023). However, teacher-focused performance evidence relied heavily on the quality of the teacher-generated products, such as teacher-generated quiz quality (Elkins et al., 2024), coverage of teacher-generated student profiles (Jin et al., 2025), or quality of teacher-authored dialogue scenarios (Choi et al., 2024), with limited investigation of the underlying teaching processes to evidently demonstrate teaching effectiveness or skill development of teachers. Although such findings may indicate that teacher-facing AI tools support task-specific skills, the absence of longitudinal studies restricts our understanding of whether these tools contribute to sustained improvements in teachers' practice and their competence.

Fig.21 The relationship between empirical data sources (columns) and their corresponding analysis methods (rows), expressed as percentages.

5. Discussion

This deliverable presented the TAICo Teacher-AI Taxonomy and a systematic literature review of teacher-facing AI tools. The aim of the systematic literature review is to verify the AI taxonomy proposed in D3.1 and to understand the current landscape of teacher-facing AI applications. To achieve this, we reviewed 103 papers that applied teacher-facing AI in teaching practice, analysing them using the AI Agent Characterisation Dimension and Teacher-AI Interaction Dimension identified in the taxonomy. Characteristics from these two dimensions were then mapped onto each other to investigate potential relationships between the technical and interactional characteristics.

In addition to examining the taxonomy-based characteristics, we also investigated other factors related to design, development, and deployment such as ecological validity, technology readiness, design approaches, and ethical considerations. Furthermore, we synthesised the reported impacts of teacher-facing AI across the reviewed literature, offering an overview of the current evidence base on the effectiveness of these tools.

The results suggest that although existing teacher-facing AI systems demonstrate effectiveness in various contexts, most tools remain at lower levels of teacher–AI teaming, functioning primarily as replacements for or complements to certain teaching tasks. While they may help teachers complete tasks more quickly and efficiently in the short term, it is difficult to argue for their contribution to long-term competence development of teachers and may even risk contributing to deprofessionalisation of the teaching profession due to limited teacher agency they allow (Yan et al., 2025).

To work toward an augmented teacher–AI hybrid system, we recommend exploring higher levels of teacher–AI teaming to safeguard teacher agency in their interactions with AI tools. Achieving this requires that AIED designers, developers, and researchers leverage more advanced and complex AI techniques, architectures and design features for interfaces that allow teachers to maintain control over the pedagogical decisions made by AIED systems. A more detailed discussion of these findings is presented in the following sections.

AI affordances for different levels of teaming

Based on the results, the majority of the tools were used at the situational and operational levels. We find that there is a lack of examples showcasing praxical and synergistic teaming between teachers and AI to support teaching tasks in the reviewed papers. Synergistic teaming refers to situations in which teachers and AI act proactively in mutual and engaging negotiation with shared agency. The ability to share the agency can give rise to constructive debate, leading to creative solutions. In the process, it is important that both AI agents and teachers can present their “mental models” to each other to allow representation sharings (Premack & Woodruff, 1978). To clarify the teaming between AI and teachers, we draw on well-established theories of human–human interaction, particularly Theory of Mind (ToM). Theory of Mind refers to the ability to understand and reason about the mental states of others, enabling individuals to predict others’ actions, resolve ambiguities and maintain communications, and coordinate their contributions during joint tasks (Premack & Woodruff, 1978). However, it is not yet clear whether current AIED systems possess the capability to genuinely present, understand, and reason the “mental models” behind decisions. One line of argument concerns the philosophical stance on whether AI has agency in the first place (Floridi, 2024), and another concerns its current technical capabilities, which rely on pre-trained data and methods without any built-in intentionality. In our review, we attempted to map agent types onto levels of teaming in previous literature (Table 4) and found that each level of teaming may potentially require a minimum capability of a type of AI agent. For instance, at the situational level of teaming, at least a model-based agent is needed to analyse data collected from the teaching context and provide contextual information for teachers. At the operational level, a goal-based agent is needed to process the goal information provided by teachers. Although we did not find any examples at the synergistic level of teaming, we

assume that this level may require more advanced agents capable of holding their own agency through building and presenting a “mental model.”

The review results also illustrate two main types of AI agents: model-based agents relying on supervised machine learning to capture students’ knowledge and skills, and utility/goal-based agents using GenAI to prepare learning materials. For the first type, most agents are fixed (non-evolutionary) supervised machine learning models aimed at capturing students’ knowledge or skills and enhancing teachers’ perception in the classroom. However, concerns remain regarding the transparency and explainability of machine learning decision-making (Cukurova et al., 2020). The hidden layers in machine learning models function as “black boxes,” encoding pedagogical inferences in ways that cannot be readily traced or explained, making it difficult for teachers to understand how specific inputs lead to particular outputs. As a result, the rationale behind system decisions often remains opaque, limiting teachers’ ability to critically evaluate reasons behind AI outputs, assess their alignment with pedagogical goals, and maintain informed oversight. Although some studies applied learning analytics techniques (e.g., the “from clicks to constructs” framework from Martinez-Maldonado et al., 2021) to make the analytical process more transparent and explainable, challenges remain regarding how to represent and communicate this process to teachers in ways they can understand in practice. In addition, given that machine learning models are trained on specific datasets, potential data biases may produce models lacking generalisability across different teaching contexts and may even introduce ethical risks (Alwahaby et al., 2022).

For agents based on GenAI, although recent research shows increasing reasoning capability in LLM-based agents, generative AI introduces an additional layer of complexity regarding interpretability, as these models are not designed to present or articulate the underlying models that guide their outputs. GenAI models are pre-trained on massive datasets and rely on probabilistic language modelling. They process prompts through iterative procedures: tokenisation (converting inputs into tokens), embedding conversion (mapping tokens into a multidimensional vector space), self-attention analysis (identifying semantic relationships among tokens), and token generation (predicting the next probable words), to formulate sentence outputs. These semantic-relationship mining and probabilistic mechanisms may limit their ability to authentically “push back,” as GenAI models do not possess an internal epistemic stance, and there is insufficient evidence that such a stance can emerge from training itself.

In addition, the evolutionary capability of models is a challenge for moving toward higher levels of teaming. For instance, both utility-based agents and learning agents require the ability to evolve based on teachers’ input. However, this capability is rarely found in current teacher-facing AI. Most teaming occurs at the situational level through dashboards where teachers have no control over model inputs or decisions. The goals and model behaviours are embedded or specified initially by researchers, designers, or developers. Some systems allow teachers to manipulate the outputs (e.g., through customised dashboards or information queries) but do not allow them to modify the models themselves. The growing trend of LLMs in education provides more opportunities for model evolution, since a critical phase in training foundational GenAI models is post-training (M. X. Lee & Wang, 2024) fine-tuning, where models are instruction-tuned with human preferences. Methods such as

Reinforcement Learning with Human Feedback (RLHF) and Direct Preference Optimisation (DPO) are post-training phases in which models are aligned with human preferences. However, these approaches are still rarely implemented in current teacher-facing AI. Moreover, while these methods offer benefits, they may also further reduce models' ability to disagree or push back when engaging with human users, promoting user satisfaction and alignment instead of co-reasoning and co-construction of knowledge. That said, GenAI may still demonstrate disagreement when explicitly prompted for counterarguments, especially if such counterarguments are well-represented in pre-training corpora. Therefore, we hypothesise that GenAI, in combination with conventional AI models or techniques, could be integrated to achieve the imitation of synergistic teaming between teachers and AI in the future. GenAI offers flexibility for coping with contextual differences, whereas other models or techniques provide theoretical grounding or an epistemic stance for pushing back.

Apart from exploring more advanced AI techniques and architectures, the interaction design of teacher-facing AI is also crucial for moving toward higher levels of teaming. Through mapping agent types against levels of teaming, we found that some teacher-facing AI tools offered relatively advanced agent capabilities but were nonetheless used at lower teaming levels due to interface limitations and/or lack of training for teachers to appropriately utilise these models. For instance, several studies proposed goal-based agents built on LLMs to support teachers with learning design (e.g., Bai et al., 2024) or the provision of student feedback (e.g., Sung et al., 2025). These agents enable teachers to specify personalised criteria for the desired output. Yet, in practice, teachers often engage with these tools in a largely transactional manner, directly accepting the generated output without clearly articulating their own goals to the agent (Arvin et al., 2023). This highlights the importance of clear and carefully designed interaction pathways that explicitly guide teachers to fully utilise the agent's capabilities. Without well-structured prompts, scaffolds, or interfaces that encourage teachers to express their intentions, constraints, and pedagogical rationales, even highly capable agents may be used in a shallow way that fails to unlock their potential for synergistic teaming. At the same time, the effectiveness of these interaction designs is inherently constrained by teachers' knowledge, skills, and confidence in working with AI systems. Limited understanding of how the agent operates, uncertainty about how to frame goals, or broader digital literacy challenges can restrict the degree to which teachers engage in higher-level teaming. Based on the review results, almost 60% of the studies did not provide onboarding or technical support for teachers to better use the tools. Professional development is therefore necessary to nurture teachers' competence to be AI-competent and be able to make sense of and act upon information pedagogically, engage with AI critically and reflectively, and develop the motivation to use AI meaningfully in alignment with their professional goals.

Lack of evidence for design and development

A critical issue highlighted by this deliverable is that the evidence base for teacher-facing AI tools still relies heavily on student-related data, even though these tools are intended to support teachers' practice. Within the experimental studies, students emerged as the most common participants (61.5%), with impacts frequently assessed through learners' performance outcomes or motivational and affective measures. While such evidence is informative for understanding downstream effects of teaching practices, it cannot substitute for robust evaluations of the completion of teaching tasks or teachers' knowledge and

competence growth. Less than half of the studies evaluate the impact by measuring changes in teaching behaviours (30.1%) or teaching effectiveness (33.0%). Because teacher-facing AI systems aim to enhance teachers' pedagogical competence, evidence should also be grounded directly in teacher-level outcomes. The overreliance on student-based proxies risks masking whether improvements are genuinely attributable to changes in teaching quality or merely reflect short-term novelty or peripheral engagement with the tools.

The deliverable also highlights a notable imbalance in the methodological approaches used to evaluate the impact of teacher-facing AI tools, with teacher-related evidence being predominantly qualitative. Approaches such as interviews, focus groups, and think-aloud protocols provide valuable depth, offering nuanced understandings of teachers' perceptions, experiences, and contextualised challenges. However, these qualitative insights are often not complemented by quantitative analyses capable of demonstrating measurable changes in teachers' behaviours or teaching performance. This lack of quantitative rigour limits the field's ability to generalise findings, compare effectiveness across tools, or trace impact over the long term. To strengthen the evidence base for evaluating teacher-facing AI, future research should incorporate more quantitative approaches.

In addition to the methodological imbalance, the evidence base is also heavily skewed toward self-reported data. Many studies rely on questionnaires that measure perceived usefulness, usability, workload, or self-efficacy. While such measures provide essential information about teacher acceptance and subjective experience, they cannot establish whether the tools lead to authentic changes in teaching processes or instructional quality. Objective measures are used in only a small proportion of studies, such as time spent on specific tasks (Jacobs et al., 2024), task performance metrics (Kang et al., 2025), and behavioural changes in the teaching process (Demszky et al., 2025). These objective indicators are crucial for capturing actual behavioural engagement, teaching task completion, and competence development which are dimensions that are rarely visible through self-report alone. The field therefore needs to integrate more objective evidence from multimodal measurements to complement teachers' subjective experiences (e.g. Divjak et al., 2025; Mendoza et al., 2022). Doing so will enable a more comprehensive and reliable evaluation of how teacher-facing AI tools influence real teaching practices and professional growth.

To advance the evidence base, future studies should incorporate multidimensional and triangulated teacher-focused metrics. Beyond task performance measures, it is essential to assess changes in teachers' competence. Currently, almost no studies provide evidence on how teacher-facing AI influences competence development in teaching tasks. On the one hand, there is a lack of validated instruments for evaluating teacher competence in the context of AI-supported practice. Competence constructs are inherently multifaceted and difficult to operationalise (Zhang & Tian, 2025). Existing measurement tools often capture broad perceptions or isolated task outputs rather than deeper, process-oriented dimensions of teaching expertise. Without instruments tailored to AI-mediated teaching, it is challenging to generate rigorous and comparable measures of competence development. On the other hand, meaningful changes in teaching competence typically unfold over extended periods, making them difficult to capture in short-term or single-session studies. Competence growth requires repeated practice, reflection, and the integration of new strategies into everyday instruction. The predominance of short-term interventions (57.3%) in the current literature

therefore limits the ability to observe longitudinal trajectories or sustained improvements in teacher competence resulting from AI tool use. Long-term research designs are necessary to understand whether teacher-facing AI tools support durable shifts in teachers' professional practice rather than temporary, task-specific gains.

Ethical consideration in the design and development process

The deliverable reveals a striking lack of attention to ethical considerations in the design, development, and deployment of teacher-facing AI systems, with fewer than 10% of studies reporting any form of ethical reflection. Ethical issues in AI for education have been emphasised extensively in research publications (Alwahaby et al., 2022; Holmes et al., 2022; Yan et al., 2025) and policy documents (Cukurova & Miao, 2024; Unesco, 2022), as they are foundational to ensuring that AI tools are trustworthy, pedagogically aligned, and supportive of equitable teaching and learning environments.

First, ethical issues should be examined across both the AI Agent Characterisation and the Teacher-AI Interaction Dimension of AI within specific teaching contexts, rather than being reduced to abstract or generic principles. From a technical perspective, issues such as data privacy, model transparency, bias mitigation, accountability, and explainability directly influence how AI systems behave and the reliability of their outputs (Holmes et al., 2022). Yet ethics also emerge through interaction: how teachers collaborate with AI, how authority and responsibility are distributed, how decision-making is negotiated, and how trust is formed. The levels of teacher–AI teaming provide a useful taxonomy for considering ethical issues within specific contexts. At lower levels of teaming, where AI provides automatic outputs or processed data, ethical risks may centre on data bias, algorithmic accuracy, model transparency, and potential erosion of autonomy. At higher levels, although some risks may be mitigated through teachers' active engagement in joint decision-making, new concerns arise, such as ambiguity in accountability within these collaborative processes. Considering ethics through these two dimensions ensures that both the system's internal mechanisms and the sociotechnical dynamics of teacher–AI interaction are adequately scrutinised.

Second, ethical considerations must be embedded proactively throughout the design and development process, rather than being confined to research ethics. Ethics in system design is distinct from ethics in research, the former concerns how the tool influences practice and power relations, while the latter concerns consent, confidentiality, and participant protection. Both are essential, but design-oriented ethical reflection is notably missing from the current evidence base. In the reviewed studies, ethical reflections mainly focused on issues related to research procedures. Fewer than 10% of papers discussed how ethical principles informed the technical development or iterative design of the AI systems. This oversight risks producing tools that are technically functional but ethically misaligned with educational values. Ethical design requires early involvement of teachers and educational experts, participatory processes that surface value tensions, iterative evaluations of how design decisions affect autonomy and agency, and continuous monitoring of ethical risks during real-world use.

Overall, the limited reporting of ethics in teacher-facing AI tools underscores a critical gap. Addressing ethical issues systematically will be vital for building AI tools that genuinely

support teachers, respect their professional judgement, and foster sustainable, trustworthy educational ecosystems.

Importance of co-designing with teachers

The finding that over 70% of AI design studies did not mention the involvement of stakeholders in the initial design and further development of AI tools, underscores a critical gap in the development of teacher-facing AI tools. Given that teachers are the primary end-users whose professional decisions, workflows, and instructional contexts these systems are meant to support, their limited involvement in design raises concerns about usability, pedagogical alignment, and real-world relevance. Co-design with teachers is essential not only for ensuring that AI tools fit authentically into classroom practice but also for identifying practical constraints, anticipating ethical implications, and aligning system capabilities with teachers’ actual needs (Alfredo et al., 2024). Without meaningful teacher participation throughout the design process, AI systems risk reinforcing unrealistic assumptions, introducing unanticipated burdens, or failing to support the complex decision-making processes inherent in teaching. At the same time, co-design sessions serve not only as a method for shaping the technology but also as an opportunity for teachers to build agency, develop AI literacy, and engage in critical pedagogical reflection, which ultimately strengthening their readiness to integrate innovative technologies and supporting the long-term sustainability of AIED tools (Nazaretsky, 2026). Therefore, more exploration is needed to foster this reciprocal approach that both elicit educators’ input for design decisions, and simultaneously supports educators’ professional growth in the future work in teacher-facing AI systems.

Table.5 A summary of the identified limitation and their implication for teacher-AI teaming

Limitation	Description	Implication for teacher-AI teaming
AI Affordance		
Predominance of situational and operational support	Most teacher-facing AI tools operate at situational (e.g., dashboards, analytics) or operational levels (e.g., task automation), with few examples of higher-level teaming	Limits teacher–AI teaming to information provision or task execution, preventing the emergence of shared agency and synergistic teaming
Low transparency and explainability of ML-based agents	Supervised ML models often function as “black boxes,” with hidden layers encoding pedagogical inferences that are difficult to trace	Reduces teachers’ ability to critically evaluate AI outputs, assess pedagogical alignment, and maintain informed oversight, weakening trust and agency
Limited interpretability of GenAI systems	GenAI models generate outputs through probabilistic language modelling without explicit epistemic grounding or explainable reasoning	Probabilistic language modelling without explicit epistemic grounding or explainable reasoning Hinders AI’s ability to authentically “push back,” justify decisions, or

		engage in epistemic dialogue with teachers
Lack of AI capability to present or reason about “mental models”	Current AIED systems lack the ability to explicitly represent, communicate, or reason about the assumptions, goals, or rationales underlying their decisions	Constrains mutual understanding and negotiation between teachers and AI, undermining conditions necessary for shared agency and constructive debate
Absence of evolutionary or adaptive learning mechanisms	Most teacher-facing AI systems do not evolve based on teachers’ feedback or preferences during use	Restricts progression toward higher levels of teaming that require adaptation, co-learning, and refinement of shared practices
Transactional interaction design	Interfaces often encourage teachers to accept AI outputs without articulating goals, constraints, or pedagogical rationales	Results in shallow use of advanced agents, preventing meaningful engagement and underutilising AI capabilities
Design, Develop, and Deployment Factors		
Limited co-design with teachers	Over 70% of studies report no stakeholder involvement	Tools may misalign with real teaching needs, workflows, and values. Also, teachers missed opportunity for professional development
Insufficient scaffolding and onboarding	Many studies do not provide training, prompts, or guidance to support effective AI use	Limits teachers’ ability to engage in higher-level teaming and exacerbates inequalities in AI competence
Gaps in teacher AI competence and professional development	Teachers may lack the knowledge, skills, or confidence to work critically with AI systems	Constrains the practical realisation of synergistic teaming, even when technically capable agents are available
Evidence Base		
Overreliance on student-based outcomes	Most evaluations assess student performance rather than teaching task completion or teacher competence	Masks whether AI genuinely enhances teaching quality or teacher competence and practice
Predominance of qualitative and self-reported data	Interviews and surveys dominate, with limited quantitative or objective measures	Limits generalisability, comparability, and the ability to trace sustained impact on teaching practices
Lack of validated competence measures	Few instruments exist to capture AI-mediated teacher competence growth	Makes it difficult to evaluate whether AI supports deeper professional learning beyond task

		efficiency
Predominance of short-term interventions	Most studies are single-session or short-term	Prevents observation of longitudinal competence development and durable changes in practice
Ethical Consideration		
Ethics was examined generally	Ethical issues are rarely analysed in relation to AI agency, authority, and control	Misses context-specific ethical risks, especially at higher levels of teacher–AI collaboration
Ethics confined to research compliance	Ethical principles rarely inform system design or iteration	Risks reinforcing power imbalances and undermining teacher autonomy and trust

6. Connection to other WPs

6.1. The role of the teacher-facing AI taxonomy in developing the TAICo model

The TAICo WP1 aims to develop and refine a comprehensive model that enhances our understanding of the complementary relationships between teachers and AI in education. The initial TAICo model identifies five key aspects: complementarity in the hybrid intelligent system, contextual information, teacher characteristics, characteristics of the AIED system, and characteristics of the AIED system’s deployment.

Fig.22 The initial version of TAICo Model

D3.1 provided a more comprehensive aspects of the framework for describing the characteristics of the AIED system within the TAICo model. For example, the characteristics identified in the initial TAICo model focused mainly on the technical aspects of the AIED system while overlooking the different types of interactions it supports. Considering the integration of AI in education from a sociotechnical perspective, the interaction between the AIED system and human teachers plays an important role in understanding their mutual relationship and the changes teachers may experience at different levels. Therefore, the taxonomy proposed in D3.1 constitutes a significant enhancement to the initial TAICo model. It helps with the specification of other aspects in the TAICo model. For instance, the five levels of teaming can be mapped onto teachers' changes at different levels in the TAICo model to clarify the interrelationships between AIED systems and complementarity within hybrid intelligent systems. These levels of teaming can also be used to specify teacher characteristics, including the knowledge and skills required of teachers as well as those supported by the hybrid system. Moreover, the levels of teaming provide an analytical lens for examining the ethical and social considerations of integrating AIED across different teaching scenarios.

Meanwhile, the systematic literature review also offers insights into the relationships between the different aspects identified in the TAICo model. For instance, the review reveals connections between various levels of teacher–AI teaming and the task-level changes experienced by teachers, as reported in previous studies. These findings can support further investigation into the mutual influences between the characteristics of AIED systems and complementarity within hybrid intelligent systems.

It is also worth noting that, building on the results of D3.1, WP1 will conduct a more detailed analysis of complementarity levels in AI use across TAICo cases. In this deliverable, teacher–AI teaming levels are primarily characterised at the level of broader teaching tasks, such as providing feedback for learning, conducting learning diagnostics, and generating learning designs. WP1 will further unpack these higher-level teaching tasks by examining teacher–AI interactions at more fine-grained levels, including monitoring, evaluating, and deciding.

Consequently, D3.1 contributes directly to T1.4, which focuses on evaluating the effects of AI on teachers' tasks, and to T1.5, which examines the effects of AI on teachers' skills and knowledge. The taxonomy proposed in D3.1 identifies design features from both technical and interaction perspectives. Building on this taxonomy, T1.4 and T1.5 will explore how these design features influence teachers' tasks, skills, and knowledge. For example, evaluation studies conducted by project partners will analyse how different levels of teacher–AI teaming affect task efficiency and changes in teachers' skills. In addition, through task decomposition, WP1 will investigate how different teaming levels shape or redistribute sub-tasks between teachers and AI systems.

6.2. The role of the teacher-facing AI taxonomy in different TAICo studies

The TAICo WP2 mainly focuses on the coordination of TAICo use cases and different types of TAICo studies, including observational studies, design studies, and evaluation studies. The taxonomy identified in the D3.1 provides a common language to describe different types of AIED system across TAICo use cases and different types of studies. By using this common

language, WP2 can synthesise results from different studies. Positioned here, this section clarifies how the findings of the D3.1 are intended to inform and structure subsequent empirical and design work across the project.

For instance, in observational studies, the taxonomy contributes to understanding the types of AIED systems used in TAICo cases in a clear and structured manner. This structured overview helps ensure that a wide range of AI types are represented within the TAICo cases. Such coverage strengthens the comprehensiveness of the project's empirical foundation and, in turn, contributes to the overall validity and robustness of the TAICo project's findings. The structured description of the AIED system also contributes to the evaluation studies in the TAICo project. By categorising systems according to their technical features and interaction types, the taxonomy enables us to systematically identify and compare the diverse AIED systems implemented across different educational contexts and their effects on teaching tasks, and teachers' skills.

In terms of the design studies, D3.1 provides a set of initial design and deployment features to be considered in the creation and development of AIED systems. More specifically, the taxonomy identifies various affordances for teacher–AI teaming offered by different AI techniques. This enables designers to map specific AI capabilities to the forms of interaction they support between teachers and AI during the design process, thereby informing and guiding key design and development decisions. In addition, the systematic literature review conducted in D3.1 highlights current gaps and limitations in the design and development of AIED systems aimed at supporting teacher–AI complementarity. These insights can guide the design studies within the TAICo project by drawing attention to underexplored design opportunities, potential challenges in implementation, and areas where further innovation is needed to enhance teacher–AI complementarity. As such, the findings of this deliverable are expected to shape the selection, analysis, and refinement of design features in TAICo use cases in subsequent WPs.

6.3. The role of the teacher-facing AI taxonomy in professional development

TAICo WP4 aims to investigate the professional training required for effective teacher–AI complementarity. D3.1 supports WP4 by identifying the different types of knowledge and skills that teachers need, as well as those that can be supported, when working with various types of AIED systems. This section therefore outlines how the conceptual findings of the current deliverable are expected to inform the design and focus of professional development activities in WP4.

On the one hand, teachers require different forms of knowledge and skills depending on the nature of their interaction with the AIED system. For example, at a situational level of teaming, teachers need the ability to critically interpret the visualisations and analytics generated by the AIED system and to translate this information into appropriate pedagogical actions. While at an operational level of teaming, teachers must be able to define, adjust, and communicate goals or tasks to the AIED system, integrating both technical understanding and pedagogical considerations. By categorising different levels of teacher–AI teaming, the taxonomy provides a structured basis for identifying the specific goals of teacher professional

training and tailoring training programmes accordingly. More details can be found in TAICo D4.1.

On the other hand, the taxonomy also supports the identification of the types of professional development that may be facilitated by teacher-facing AI systems themselves. For instance, based on the results of the literature review, AIED systems that support situational teaming can help teachers enhance their competence in perceiving and interpreting students' learning processes, while systems that support operational teaming may contribute to teachers' ability to deliver personalised feedback or orchestrate adaptive learning activities. In this way, the taxonomy not only clarifies teachers' training needs but also sheds light on how AIED systems can actively contribute to teachers' ongoing professional growth.

6.4. The role of the teacher-facing AI taxonomy in the ethical assessment

D3.1 also provides important contributions to WP6, which examines the ethical issues related to the TAICo project. By offering a structured taxonomy of AIED system characteristics and levels of teacher–AI teaming, D3.1 helps clarify where ethical considerations may emerge in the design, deployment, and use of AIED systems. For instance, understanding how teachers interact with AI in different ways allows WP6 to identify potential risks related to transparency, accountability, data privacy, and the fair distribution of responsibilities between teachers and AI in different TAICo use cases. Additionally, the taxonomy's emphasis on system affordances and interaction types enables a more detailed analysis of where power imbalances, over-reliance on AI, or unintended biases may occur. In this way, D3.1 offers an initial lens that supports WP6 in developing context-sensitive ethical guidelines and safeguards that ensure responsible and trustworthy implementation of AIED systems in educational practice.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

This deliverable has presented the development of the TAICo Teacher-facing AI Taxonomy and a systematic literature review on the existing teacher-facing AI. Situated within Work Package 3, D3.1 responds to the need for a structured and evidence-informed understanding of how teacher-facing AI systems are designed, developed, and deployed across diverse educational contexts.

By combining a systematic literature review with the iterative development of an AI taxonomy, this work provides a comprehensive overview of the current landscape of teacher-facing AI technologies. The taxonomy identifies key characteristics and dimensions across the AI design, development, and deployment process that influence the effectiveness, efficacy, and ethical use of AI in education. Importantly, the iterative interplay between the taxonomy and the systematic review ensured both conceptual rigor and empirical grounding. The predefined taxonomy features guided the coding and analysis of the reviewed studies, while empirical evidence from the literature informed the refinement and validation of the taxonomy itself.

The results of the systematic review highlight both prevailing design patterns and critical gaps in existing teacher-facing AI systems, particularly with respect to human-centred design, ethical considerations, and the different levels of teacher–AI interactions. Building on these insights, the initial insights and suggestions generated in this deliverable offer direction for the future design and development of AI systems that aim to complement, rather than replace, teachers’ professional agency, expertise, and responsibilities.

As the first deliverable of WP3, D3.1 establishes a foundational framework that informs subsequent tasks and deliverables within the work package and beyond. The AI taxonomy and the insights from the systematic literature review will directly support the design and development of AI interfaces in Task 3.3, and be further refined through stakeholder engagement and co-design activities in Task 3.2 to develop the TAICo Design Guidelines.

Meanwhile, D3.1 also contributes to the TAICo project by strengthening the conceptual, empirical, and methodological connections across multiple work packages. It significantly enhances the initial TAICo model developed in WP1 by providing a comprehensive taxonomy of teacher-facing AIED system characteristics that extends beyond technical features to explicitly include the levels of teacher–AI teaming. This enables clearer specification of relationships between AIED systems, teacher characteristics, contextual factors, and complementarity within hybrid intelligent systems. In addition, D3.1 directly supports T1.4 and T1.5 by identifying technical and interactional design features that can be examined in relation to changes in teachers’ tasks, skills, and knowledge. Beyond WP1, the taxonomy provides WP2 with a shared language to describe and compare AIED systems across use cases and study types, thereby enabling synthesis of findings from observational, design, and evaluation studies. D3.1 also informs design studies by highlighting affordances for teacher–AI teaming and identifying gaps and limitations in current AIED system design, guiding future innovation. Furthermore, D3.1 contributes to WP4 by supporting the clarification of the knowledge and skills teachers require at different levels of teaming and identification ways in which AIED systems can support teachers’ professional development, as further elaborated in D4.1. Finally, D3.1 supports WP6 by offering a structured framework for identifying ethical risks and considerations associated with different AI characteristics and levels of teaming, thereby enabling the development of context-sensitive ethical guidelines for responsible teacher-facing AI.

Future work will build on the foundations established in D3.1 by extending and operationalising its insights in several directions. First, the AI taxonomy and evidence base will be iteratively expanded to include a broader range of teacher-facing AI tools, moving beyond research prototypes to incorporate commercially available and practice-based systems currently used in real educational settings. This will enable a more comprehensive and ecologically valid understanding of how AI is designed and deployed for teachers in everyday practice. Second, the findings, limitations, and design suggestions identified in this deliverable will inform co-design activities with the EdTech sectors. Through iterative engagement with designers, developers, and educators, the TAICo design guidelines will be refined to ensure they are actionable, context-sensitive, and aligned with both pedagogical values and technical feasibility. Third, future design and development efforts will explicitly target AI systems that support higher levels of teacher–AI teaming, moving beyond situational and operational

support toward more synergistic forms of collaboration. This includes exploring AI capabilities, and interface designs that enable shared agency, mutual reasoning, and meaningful negotiation between teachers and AI, thereby advancing the realisation of teacher–AI complementarity in educational practice.

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<https://doi.org/10.1145/3626252.3630759>

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Appendix:

Appendix 1: Reviews of AI in education

No	Reference	Teacher/earner-focused	Focused Context	Technology	Taxonomy/Coding schemes (if any)
1	Sarwari, K. (2024). Using AI Tools for Teaching and Learning: A Systematic Review of Literature. Journal of Cognition Emotion and Education, Online First. https://doi.org/10.22034/cee.2024.491255.1031	Both	HE	-	Explore advantages (1. Effective teaching and learning, 2. precise feedback and evaluation, 3. personalized learning, 4. facilitate access to learning, 5. students' academic performance, 6 data analysis, 7. enhance administrative tasks and 8. effective teaching approaches) and disadvantages (1. Loss of creativity, 2. technological limitation, 3. limits human interaction, 4. Harmful content and disseminating false information, 5. Ethical issues such as transparency, accessibility and biases, 6. Data privacy)
2	Ali, Z. (2020). Artificial Intelligence (AI): A Review of its Uses in Language Teaching and Learning. IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, 769(1), 012043. https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/769/1/012043	Both	Language learning	-	Applications of AI in language learning context
3	Lameras, P., & Arnab, S. (2021). Power to the Teachers: An Exploratory Review on Artificial Intelligence in Education. Information, 13(1), 14. https://doi.org/10.3390/info13010014	Teachers	-	-	AI meanings and techniques, AI for teaching and learning in schools, Designing and orchestrating teaching with the use of AI, Applications of AI in teaching and learning, AI and teacher competencies, capabilities, and skills, Ethical AI in education; conceptualised using the Substitution, Augmentation, Modification Redefinition (SAMR) model
4	Holmes, W., & Tuomi, I. (2022). State of the art and practice in AI in education. European Journal of Education, 57(4), 542–570. https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12533	Both	-	-	Focus on end-users' applications: student-focused AIED, teacher-focused AIED (1. Plagiarism detection, 2. Smart Curation of Learning Materials, 3. Classroom Monitoring, 4. Automatic Summative Assessment, 5. AI Teaching Assistant (including assessment assistant) and 6. Classroom Orchestration), and institution-focused AIED
5	Salas-Pilco, S., Xiao, K., & Hu, X. (2022). Artificial Intelligence and Learning Analytics in Teacher Education: A Systematic Review. Education Sciences, 12(8), 569. https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12080569	Teachers	Teacher education	AI and LA	Goals/objectives, participants, data sources, techniques, tools (ai tools, online platforms, data analysis tools and monitoring tools), ethical procedures, results
6	Baidoo-Anu, D., & Ansah, L. O. (2023). Education in the Era of Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI): Understanding the Potential Benefits of ChatGPT in Promoting Teaching and Learning. Journal of AI, 7(1).	Both	-	ChatGPT	
7	Gentile, M., Città, G., Perna, S., & Allegra, M. (2023). Do we still need teachers? Navigating the paradigm shift of the teacher's role in the AI era. Frontiers in Education, 8, 1161777. https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1161777	Teachers	-	-	analyzes the change in the teacher's role triggered by the integration of AI into educational systems; coded on 1. Teacher-student interaction, 2. Teaching methods and strategies, 3. Teaching content, 4. Students' assessment and monitoring, 5. Teachers' professional development
8	Jamal, D. A. (2023). The Role Of Artificial Intelligence (AI) In Teacher Education: Opportunities & Challenges. 10(1).	Teachers	Teacher education	-	role of AI in teacher education, including its potential benefits, drawbacks, and challenges.

9	Labadze, L., Grigolia, M., & Machaidze, L. (2023). Role of AI chatbots in education: Systematic literature review. <i>International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education</i> , 20(1), 56. https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00426-1	Both	-	Chatbots	Pros and cons of chatbots for students and educators
10	Murphy, R. F. (2019). Artificial Intelligence Applications to Support K–12 Teachers and Teaching (Perspective: Expert Insights on a Timely Policy Issue). RAND Corporation. http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep19907	Teachers	K-12	-	AI applications include (1) providing differentiated instruction and feedback in mixed-ability classrooms, (2) providing students with timely feedback on their writing products, or (3) identifying students who may be struggling to learn and make progress toward graduation.
11	Zhang, K., & Aslan, A. B. (2021). AI technologies for education: Recent research & future directions. <i>Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence</i> , 2, 100025. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100025	Both	-	-	Review AIED applications and potential benefits
12	Malik, M. A., & Shah, R. (2025). AI teachers (AI-based robots as teachers): History, potential, concerns and recommendations. <i>Frontiers in Education</i> , 10, 1541543. https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2025.1541543	Teachers	-	AI-based robots	
13	Mittal, U., Sai, S., Chamola, V., & Sangwan, D. (2024). A Comprehensive Review on Generative AI for Education. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 12, 142733–142759. https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3468368	-	-	GenAI (GANs)	Game generators, image generators, video generators, 3d visual generators, audio generators, code generators, text generators.
14	Crompton, H., & Burke, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence in higher education: The state of the field. <i>International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education</i> , 20(1), 22. https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00392-8	Both	HE	-	
15	Fu, Y., & Weng, Z. (2024). Navigating the ethical terrain of AI in education: A systematic review on framing responsible human-centered AI practices. <i>Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence</i> , 7, 100306. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100306	Both and more stakeholders	Ethical/responsible AI	-	
16	Wang, S., Wang, F., Zhu, Z., Wang, J., Tran, T., & Du, Z. (2024). Artificial intelligence in education: A systematic literature review. <i>Expert Systems with Applications</i> , 252, 124167. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.124167	Both	-	-	Applications (adaptive learning and personalised tutoring; intelligent assessment and management; profiling and prediction; emergent technologies or products), research topics (system and application design; adoption and acceptance of AIED; impacts of AIED; challenges of AIED), research methods (mixed methods; qualitative study; experimental study; statistical analysis; survey research; descriptive analysis); theory use (none; marginal use; substantial use), educational context (general; HE; K-12; preschool)
17	Mai, D. T. T., Da, C. V., & Hanh, N. V. (2024). The use of ChatGPT in teaching and learning: A systematic review	Both	-	ChatGPT	

	through SWOT analysis approach. <i>Frontiers in Education</i> , 9, 1328769. https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1328769				
18	Wang, N., Wang, X., & Su, Y.-S. (2024). Critical analysis of the technological affordances, challenges and future directions of Generative AI in education: A systematic review. <i>Asia Pacific Journal of Education</i> , 44(1), 139–155. https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2024.2305156	Both	-	GenAI	Roles of GenAI (intelligence tutor, tutee, learning tool/partnet, domain expert)
19	Chen, L., Chen, P., & Lin, Z. (2020). Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Review. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 8, 75264–75278. https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2988510	Both	-	-	Scenarios of AI education and AI-related techniques; functions AI provides in educational scenarios (administration, instruction, learning)
20	Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V. I., Bond, M., & Gouverneur, F. (2019). Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators? <i>International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education</i> , 16(1), 39. https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0	Both	HE	-	
21	Huang, J., Saleh, S., & Liu, Y. (2021). A Review on Artificial Intelligence in Education. <i>Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies</i> , 10(3), 206. https://doi.org/10.36941/ajis-2021-0077	Both	-	-	Applications of AIED (adaptive learning, teaching evaluation, virtual classroom, smart campus, and intelligent tutoring robots.)
22	Humble, N., & Mozelius, P. (2019). Teacher-Supported AI or AI-Supported Teachers? <i>Proceedings of the European Conference on the Impact of Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (ECIAIR)</i> , 157–164. https://doi.org/10.34190/ECIAIR.19.007	Teachers	-	-	Teacher-supported AI (e.g., ITS, virtual agents), AI-supported teachers (e.g., smart classrooms, ITS?), and teacher-compatible AI (digital assistant)
23	Seo, K., Yoo, M., Dodson, S., & Jin, S.-H. (2024). Augmented teachers: K–12 teachers' needs for artificial intelligence's complementary role in personalized learning. <i>Journal of Research on Technology in Education</i> , 1–18. https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2024.2330525	Both	K-12	-	Affordances (pedagogy, administration, subject content)

Appendix 2: Coding schemes for our systematic literature review

Section	Sub-section	Question	Choices	References
AI (RQ1)	1. Data modality	Which data modalities were collected by the AI system?	Text; Ratings; Log data; video; audio; physiological data; eye-tracking; skin sensing; location sensing; other	Alwahaby et al (2022)
	2. Data context	Who was the data collected from?	Students; teachers; learning context; others	
	3. Model type	Is the main model symbolic (human-generated rules), statistical (uses data) or hybrid?	symbolic; statistical; hybrid; others	OECD (2022)
	3.1 Symbolic AI	Explain how the symbolic AI was built		
	3.2 Statistical AI	Determine whether the model is supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, reinforcement learning or deep learning?	Supervised learning; Unsupervised learning; Semi-supervised learning; Reinforcement learning; Deep learning; Other	JRC (2022)
	3.3 Hybrid AI	Explain the statistical and symbolic components. Note any training paradigms.	RAG: Retrieval-Augmented Generation; (Training paradigms) - SLHF: Supervised Learning from Human Feedback; (Training paradigms) - RLHF: Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback; Prompt engineering; In-context learning - Zero-shot/few-shot learning; (Model adaptation technique) - LoRA: Low-Rank Adaptation; (Model adaptation technique) - QLoRA: Quantized LoRA; RLVR: Reinforcement learning with variable rewards; other	
	4. Model evolution	Does the model evolve and / or acquire abilities from interacting with data in the field?	No evolution during operation (no interaction); Evolution during operation through active interaction; Evolution during operation through passive interaction	OECD (2022)
	5. AI Tasks	What did the system do?	Recognition; Event detection; Forecasting; Personalisation; Intelligent UI; Goal-driven optimisation; Reasoning with knowledge structures; content generation; other	OECD (2022)
	6. Interface	In which formats was the design interface offered to teachers?	Textual feedback; Dashboard/visualisations; chatbot; speech agents; immersive devices/environment; other	
	7. Output timing	When did the AI system provide information to teachers?	Before teaching; during teaching; after teaching; other	
	8. Design	Were any stakeholders engaged with the design process? If so, how?	No; teachers; students; developers; need to check the referred paper; other (how they were involved?)	
9. AI ethics	Did the paper mention any ethics issues related to the	Governance/Stewardship; Transparency/Accountability; Sustainability/Proportionality; Privacy; Safety/Security;	Nguyen et al (2023)	

		use/development of the AI tools? Is so, what were they?	Inclusiveness/Fairness; Human-centred/Autonomy; other. across designing/development; deployment phase	
	10. Agent type	What is the type of AI agent used in this study? (From Russell and Norvig)	Simple reflex agent; Model-based agent; Goal-based agent; Utility-based agent; Learning agent;	Russell and Norvig (1995)
	11. Model performance	Are any performance results for the AI models provided?		
Interaction space (RQ2)	1. Teaming Level	What is the level of teacher-AI teaming presented in this study?	- Transactional; Situational; Operational; Praxical; Synergistic; Other	
	2. Interaction	Explain teacher-AI interactions		
	3. Scaffolding	Were there any design features of the AI system to scaffold teacher-AI interaction?	No; Other;	
	4. Teaching task	What teaching tasks were supported by the AI system?	Conceptualisation; Authoring; Implementation; Regulation; Evaluation; Reflection	Pishtari and Rodríguez-Triana (2022)
	5. Complementarity	Were the task being replaced, complemented or augmented?	Replacement; Complement; Augmentation	Cukurova (2025)
Deployment Context (RQ3)	1. Subject	What is the subject of the teaching and learning context examined in the study?	STEM; Art/Humanities/Social sciences; Business/Management/Interdisciplinary; Not specified; Others	
	2. Educational levels	What is the educational level of the students involved in the teaching and learning context examined in the study?	Early childhood; Primary; Secondary; Higher education; vocational education; lifelong learning/workplace training/informal learning; Not specified; Others	
	3. Country	Which country was the study conducted in?		
	4. Delivery mode	What was the mode of instructional delivery in the teaching and learning context examined in the study?	Online; Face-to-face; Hybrid; Blended; Not specified; Others	
	5. Instructional strategies	What teaching and learning approaches or instructional strategies were employed in the study?	1. Instructor-Centered Learning; 2. Interactive Learning; 3. Individualized Learning; 4. Experiential Learning; Not specified; Other	Weston and Cranton (1986)
	6. Ecological validity	To what extent does the study reflect real-world teaching and learning	Lab-based; Near real-world; Real-world; not specified; other	

		conditions or authentic educational settings?		
	7. Technology readiness level	What was the AI's technology readiness level?	TRL 1-9 (1- Basic principles observed, 2- Technology concept formulated, 3- Experimental proof of concept, 4- Technology validated in lab, 5- Technology validated in relevant environment, 6- Technology demonstrated in relevant environment, 7- System prototype demonstration in operational environment, 8-System complete and qualified, 9- Actual system proven in operational environment) ; not specified; other	TRL-EU Horizon: https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/sites/default/@les/2022-12/trl-assessment-tool-guide-@nal.pdf
	8. Business model	Is the AI system a for-profit use, non-profit use or public service system?	For profit use; Non-profit use (outside public sector); Public service (often controlled by the government; Academic/personal; Not specified; Other	OECD (2020)
	9. Onboarding and support	What support was provided to teachers to scaffold their use of the AI system?	Initial training sessions; Ongoing support or coaching; User manuals or video tutorials on how to use AI; No support mentioned; Other	OECD (2020)
	10. Constructs	What were the measured constructs of the AI system?	Teacher awareness; Teacher productivity; Learning materials; Learner awareness; Learner productivity; self-regulated learning; engagement; online activity and behaviors; knowledge & skills; Learning gains; retention & dropout; other	Knobbout and Stappen (2020)
	11. Dimension of target constructs	What are the dimensions of the target constructs?	Cognition; Metacognition; Affect; Motivation; Socio-cultural; Other of teachers; learners; others	Plass and Pawar (2020)
Evaluation (RQ4)	1. Duration	What was the duration of the intervention study?	Single session; short-term (1-3 weeks); mid-term (3-10 weeks); long-term (over 10 weeks); Not specified; other	
	2. Frequency	How frequently did teachers engage with or use AI tools in the teaching and learning context?	Use once only; Use less than once per week; weekly use; multiple times per week; daily use; not specified; other	
	3. Sample size	What was the reported sample size?		
	4. Dependent variables measured	What were the dependent variables measured?	Changes in behaviours; Impact on learning/teaching; Usefulness; Satisfaction; Usability; Adoption of teachers; learners	Ley et al (2023)
	5. Methodology	How were the impacts collected and analysed?	Observation; Self-report questionnaire; interview/focused groups; RCT/Experiment; analysed by Qualitative analysis such as thematic/content analysis; Descriptive statistics; Inferential statistics; Machine learning; Social network analysis/Epistemic analysis, sequential analysis	
	6. Research impacts	Key findings		

Appendix 3: The table of mapping TAIco use cases with the teacher-AI teaming levels

Leading Partner	Case Description	Description of Teacher-AI Interaction	Teaming Level
UOULU	MAI is a Metacognitive AI agent aimed at recognizing challenges to collaborative learning and supporting regulation of learning by inviting students to raise their metacognitive awareness through spoken prompts.	Teachers define the rules that guide MAI's analysis of learning regulation. MAI collects data during the collaborative learning process and analyses students' regulation of learning. Based on these analyses, MAI interacts with students. Teachers then monitor the interactions between MAI and students.	Operational level of Teaming
UWK	UWK case will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Phase 1) Explore the current usage and role that AI plays in the Learning Design practices of practitioners like lecturers, trainers and curriculum designers in the context of Continuing Education. • (Phase 2) Conceptualize and develop, together with the relevant practitioners, teacher-AI socio-technical tools and pedagogical approaches that aim to support the identified practices and needs. • (Phase 3) Implement the developed tools/approaches to evaluate/validate their impact through a combination of experimental and longitudinal observational studies. 	Teachers and AI jointly define learning goals and co-construct learning plans through mutual discussion.	Synergistic Level of Teaming
TLU	This case investigates how AI-enhanced learning technologies can complement teachers' abilities to design, orchestrate, and reflect on collaborative problem-solving (CPS) activities in middle school mathematics. Through real-time monitoring, adaptive scaffolding, and reflective feedback, AI augments teachers' pedagogical decision-making and supports both collaborative and individual learning processes.	The AI system collects data and analyses the collaborative learning process. The analysis results are visualised and presented to teachers. Teachers then use the information provided by the AI system to make pedagogical decisions that support collaborative learning.	Situational Level of Teaming
RU	In RU case there is the following aim: GenAI during Course design: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secondary school teachers aim to use a GenAI tool to design feedback interventions for project-based assignments. The tool is aimed to be used during the design of the project-based assignment. • The tool augments the teacher's skills by guiding the assignment outline and the reflection on critical course and learning points. It also enhances the teacher's feedback literacy informing about the different aspects of feedback interventions in terms of A) Timing B) Feedback Focus C) Feedback contingency. Lastly, it complements the feedback interventions that the teacher finally decides based on the tool proposals on different types of feedback. GenAI during course enactment:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GenAI for Course Design: Teachers request feedback from GenAI on a given course design, and GenAI provides feedback accordingly. 2. GenAI for Course Enactment: GenAI provides monitoring information on how students interact with GenAI. Teachers use this information to support learning or to adjust GenAI settings as needed. 	Transactional Level of Teaming & Operational Level of Teaming

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secondary school teachers are aimed to use a GenAI tool to monitor and control student interactions with GenAI • The tool permits the teachers to monitor student interaction with GenAI (e.g., if they copied the AI generated output, how many times they prompted etc) and finetune the prompts (e.g., increase or decrease the prompt number, the length of the AI response etc.) 		
RUB	<p>Calcularis is an adaptive educational software designed to enhance basic mathematical competencies in children. The software facilitates the acquisition of basic numerical skills, including number sense, arithmetic operations, and spatial number representation. Its adaptive algorithm continuously assesses students' progress and adjusts the difficulty of tasks accordingly.</p> <p>The software incorporates a coach (dashboard) for teachers that provides detailed student information and enables them to monitor learners' progress comprehensively by providing visual information and progress reports.</p>	Teachers initiate the AI system by choosing either a pre-defined or a free-training approach. The AI system collects data during the learning process and analyses the data based on the selected approach. The analysis results are then presented to teachers through visualisations. Teachers use the insights generated by the AI system to support learning accordingly.	Operational Level of Teaming
UCL	The Collaboration Analytics Dashboard (CAD) is designed to enhance students' awareness by providing post-hoc insights into their collaborative processes, challenge moments, and regulatory strategies exhibited during group activities. It also aims to support teachers by improving their perceptual awareness, providing help for students in a complex f2f collaborative learning context, and enabling informed instructional adaptations in multi-group classrooms.	The CAD collects data and analyses the collaborative learning process. Teachers select the features of interest and set thresholds for the alert function. Based on teachers' configurations, the AI provides information on the selected features and identifies groups at risk according to the specified thresholds.	Operational Level of Teaming

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